

RESULTS FROM RISK, CO-BENEFIT AND TRADE-OFF ASSESSMENT

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LANDMARC

Land-use based Mitigation for Resilient Climate Pathways

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Changes with respect to the DoA	<i>There are no major changes to the DoA with the exception of applying another methodology instead of MCDA and to move SDG considerations towards case study engagement. We felt that MCDA was too constraining for the type of research across very diverse land based mitigation technologies (LMTs). Thus, we applied open ended interviews and heat maps to identify the risks, co-benefit and trade-offs that appeared more frequently. See methods (section 2) of this deliverable for details. Initially we intended risks, co-benefits and trade-offs to SDGs. We proposed in the GA to account for SDGs. However, SDGs are more related to impacts, which this deliverable does not explore. We propose to case study teams to use this deliverable as a contextual basis for considering which SDGs most relate to their specific circumstance and stakeholder engagement work. This will link the more local case study context to the wider global community goals.</i>
Dissemination and uptake	<i>The target audience for this deliverable are researchers working on model (sets) and researchers working with stakeholders</i>

Short Summary of results

This deliverable assesses the risks, opportunities and trade-offs of individual LMTs. Stakeholders were interviewed across the LANDMARC consortium these aspects. We then synthesized stakeholder's perspective of risks of each LMTs and compared. The key findings are that stakeholders' perspective

highlight contextual issues that impact individuals' livelihoods as well as longer terms issues in policy consistency. We then reflected to which extent these risks could be considered in models and provides some first insights on scaling up from individual LMTs to LMT portfolios.

Evidence of accomplishment

An overview of risks per LMT is included at the end of the report. The breakdown per LMT is linked to interview with codes related to the processed interviews, which can be accessed (anonymized) in full upon request. The results from D5.2 have already informed D5.3 and D5.4 efforts.

Preface

Negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and net zero emissions policy scenarios. To date most climate actions have focused on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfill the Paris Agreement and meet the world's climate goals research, policy and markets are increasingly looking at negative emission solutions.

This is why the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work together in order to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assess the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Map their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

LANDMARC is an interdisciplinary consortium with expertise from ecology, engineering, climate sciences, global carbon cycle, soil sciences, satellite earth observation sciences, agronomy, economics, social sciences, and business. There is a balanced representation of partners from academia, SMEs, and NGOs from the EU, Africa, Asia and the Americas, which ensures a wide coverage of Land Mitigation Techniques (LMTs) operating in different contexts (e.g. climates, land-use practices, socio-economic etc.) and spatial scales.

The LANDMARC project consortium:

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Executive summary

This deliverable set out to provide LANDMARC modellers and researchers an overview of stakeholder perspectives on risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs. Climate mitigation research is often focused on a top-down approach. While important for the technical potential of climate mitigation measures, it can overlook contextual factors. We bridge this gap using qualitative research, through semi-structured interviews performed by 12 case study leads of the LANDMARC consortium.

Case study leads were provided guidance for a semi-structured interview, using a contextual categorization of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs including: technology and practice, political, institutional, policy, societal, economy, environmental, and avoided cost factors. This categorization helped structure the interview approach, while allowing for a more in-depth discussion where stakeholders could expand on the complexities of contextual risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs. Overall, 92 interviews were reported, coded, and analysed. The results were clustered into themes per LMT and through the identification of sub-cluster themes.

A deliberate focus of this approach was quality over quantity, however, the distribution across LMTs is not evenly represented. Some LMTs with a broad representation in LANDMARC, such as afforestation, was featured much more often than those with little representation. The wide variety of LMTs and cultural and contextual diversity meant that the interviews were not directly replicated across the case studies. Finally, some contextual aspects of LMT (e.g. societal risks) were not mentioned often, likely relating to uncertainty or unwillingness to engage beyond the stakeholder's expertise.

The interview findings are presented per LMT, including a summary of the D6.1 LMT literature review, and a comparison of the literature and stakeholder findings. A key finding was that the literature review focused more on technical potential and climatic risks, while stakeholders were focused more on implementation and contextual risks. Other than climatic and environmental co-benefits, covered in LANDMARC D4.1, relatively few co-benefits were mentioned by stakeholders. Very few trade-offs were mentioned, likely due to difficulties and uncertainties of comparing different options.

Modellers from the DayCent, ALCES, LandSHIFT, and E3ME models were asked to reflect on the interview findings. The DayCent, ALCES, and LandSHIFT model can use these findings for scenario building or to illustrate boundary conditions, as well as inform future stakeholder engagements with a contextual basis of the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs. The E3ME model can use the findings to assess the feasibility of their input assumptions.

The deliverable further listed some of the gaps, and avenues for further exploration based on the interview findings. The spatial and temporal dimensions were difficult topics to discuss, with the magnitude and especially mid-to long-term risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs being rarely noted. A key consideration is the trade-off between mitigation and adaptation goals, and how these might interact or counteract one another. A further observation are the dynamics over time of an LMT and

its associated risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs. The time between investments and returns on investment, long wait for co-benefits, and the associated long-term uncertainty were important insights provided by the stakeholders which should be further explored.

A further consideration for this deliverable was to set out an exploration of moving beyond individual LMTs towards considering an LMT portfolio. We provided an initial framework which could be used to further investigate LMT portfolios, while considering both qualitative and quantitative data. To advance this work we clustered the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs per LANDMARC case study portfolio, providing an indication of where future work could be focused.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

IPCC scenarios that aim to hold the global temperature to acceptable values rely on the large-scale implementation and success of a range of techniques and practices. One area is land-based climate mitigation techniques and practices (LMTs), which is a main focus for carbon sequestration (IPCC, 2022). To understand the realistic potential of LMTs, we first need to assess the risks related to implementation barriers as well as the potential impacts of LMTs.

Climate mitigation research is often focused on a deductive top-down approach. While top-down research, including the majority of modelling approaches, is important for understanding the technical potential of climate mitigation, it can overlook the social, economic, and cultural factors at the local level that influence how people respond to and engage with mitigation efforts (Conway *et al.*, 2019; van Vliet *et al.*, 2020). Qualitative research including stakeholder consultation is particularly useful for exploring these factors and providing insights into how they can be addressed.

Consulting stakeholders can help researchers, modellers, policymakers, and land-users understand the local contexts in which mitigation strategies are implemented. This can include social norms, cultural values, economic conditions, and political structures that influence how people engage with climate mitigation efforts. This approach can also help identify barriers and opportunities for effective climate mitigation and develop tailored strategies for effective climate mitigation.

This deliverable aims at improving the understanding of key socio-economic and environmental risks associated with implementing LMTs and its potential negative outcomes, as identified by stakeholders. This includes the qualitative understanding of risks, opportunities, and trade-offs of (scaling up) the different LMTs from a stakeholder perspective.

We approached this task through interviewing stakeholders in all case studies with a variety of backgrounds, LMT involvement, and perspective. This aligns well with a growing call for the involvement of stakeholders with climate change research (Conway *et al.*, 2019; Norström *et al.*, 2020).

First, stakeholders can provide insights into the relevant issues and challenges that need to be addressed for LMT implementation in different contexts. They can help researchers identify gaps in knowledge, understand the social and cultural context, and identify priorities for action. Second, involving stakeholders can enhance the relevance of research by providing diverse perspectives and ensuring that research outcomes and potential policies promoting LMTs are aligned with stakeholder needs. Stakeholders can also help researchers identify potential research biases (e.g. focusing on technical potential rather than societal feasibility). Additionally, a research design that is inclusive and accessible will also include diverse stakeholders and identify challenges in groups that have been marginalized from decision making. Third, stakeholders who are involved in the research process are more likely to understand and value the research findings and be more willing to support and implement the recommendations.

The next step was to align the outcomes of stakeholder research to modelling efforts of the LANDMARC consortium. Bottom-up (land-based) climate mitigation research can provide a detailed understanding of how land-based activities such as agroforestry, afforestation, and other LMTs contribute to climate change mitigation. This information is essential for informing the scenarios and modeling the impacts of these activities and developing more feasible and effective mitigation strategies. Thus, by incorporating a strong qualitative element informed by literature reviews (as seen LANDMARC *D6.1 Literature review of LMT potential* and LANDMARC *D6.3 LMT scaling scenarios*) and stakeholder engagement in our modelling, climate, land use and macroeconomic models can be improved to reflect the impact of land-based activities more accurately on climate change, as well as the conditions for their implementation.

For policymaking, linking bottom-up research to climate modeling can inform policy decisions by providing policymakers with a better understanding of the impacts of land-based activities on climate change the impact of these strategies on the climate, broader environment, and the economy. While qualitative risks and opportunities are not yet directly included in models, they can be considered in the scenario narrative development, which can provide insights on potential trade-offs in an LMT portfolio.

2. Framing, methodology, and results

2.1 Understanding risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs

To capture a qualitative understanding of the environmental, socio-economic and institutional risks we selected a framework for categorizing stakeholder inputs.

Risks are broadly defined as barriers to scaling up known as implementation risks or consequential risks that are ‘potential negative impacts’ (Hanger-Kopp, Lieu and Nikas, 2019). Risks are further subdivided into environmental, social, economic, political, policy risks. This exercise will help to make explicit risks that are typically overlooked because they are not easily quantifiable and to help understand risks from a qualitative perspective, more specifically to scale up LMTs.

Co-benefits are seen as ‘opportunities for positive potential impacts’ (Hanger-Kopp, Lieu and Nikas, 2019) and stakeholders can identify the potential co-benefits of LMTs including environmental, social, economic, political, policy co-benefits. Specifying both positive and negative impacts is important as risks and opportunities may not affect or accrue to the same population groups and some groups could be negatively impacted by a measure and oppose LMT implementation even though the net impacts for the wider society may be beneficial.

Understanding the potential **trade-offs** between different land-based climate mitigation options, including alternative land uses, is especially important for LMTs as they take place in a contested space. A large variety of stakeholders have different interpretations of how land should and can be used, and how they (or other sectors) will be affected by its use. One example is food security, from ensuring successful harvests for subsistence farming, to maintaining national or global food security with alternative land-use.

To capture the different aspects of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs we used the following categorization to both inform the interview process and to code and analyze the data:

1. Technology/practice parameters refer to the negative impact the technology may have on people or the environment or challenges of implementing and/or scaling up the technology (e.g. technical challenges, scalability challenges, accidents, failure of the technique to reach targets...)
2. Political parameters refer to policy choices that cause dissent and disputes among political actors and groups within the same or different jurisdictions (e.g. lack of political support, political instability, corruption...)
3. Institutional parameters refer to implementation challenges and opportunities, lack of coordination or conflict within or across institutions, or a lack of institutional legitimacy (e.g. institutional misalignment, long/tedious bureaucracy, exceptional institutional support, lack of institutional legitimacy, inclusion of LMT in national NDC...) <i>Note:</i> Institutions are defined as “formal and informal rules and norms that organise social, political and economic relations” (North, 1990). They may include policy, education, market, religious, and cultural institutions
4. Policy parameters refer to challenges and opportunities with implementing policies such as policy instruments, regulations, strategies, programmes and initiatives (e.g. poor policy)

<p>design, challenges with policy implementation, strong policy support, lack of adequate monitoring...)</p>
<p>5. Societal parameters refer to the social support or resistance towards implementing a technology such as threatening societal groups and/or creating inequalities among them (e.g. proximity of the technology to communities, social changes, local culture, lack of knowledge, resistance to behavioural change, preference for the new scape, negative health impacts, impact in daily life of locals...)</p>
<p>6. Economy-wide factors refer to the influence of policies on national economic indicators, which might affect specific stakeholders such as public or private organizations, local SHs (e.g. trade imbalances, energy security, market regulation, lack of subsidies, market domination...)</p>
<p>7. Business factors refer to specific challenges and opportunities related to running a business including investment challenges, payback periods and revenue stream (e.g. investment challenges, more diversified sources of income, high capital costs, long payback period...)</p>
<p>8. Environmental factors refer to changes in the nature/environment including human, flora and fauna ecosystems (e.g. biodiversity loss, waste issues, increase in biodiversity...)</p>
<p>9. Avoided costs derived from the implementation of LMT (e.g. avoided infrastructure expenses due to avoided soil subsidence, avoided costs in water purification because of avoided chemical substances leaching...)</p>

Table 1. Categorization of contextual factors for risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs for implementing LMTs based on North (1990).

Using these categories helped case study leads to capture the complex challenges associated with land-based climate change mitigation. Through considering a range of categories of risks, researchers conducted a comprehensive risk analysis that considers the different types of risks associated with land-based climate change mitigation. The outcomes can be shared with stakeholders to help identify potential risks that may be overlooked if only one or two risks categories are considered. This also broadens the conversation to include risks some stakeholder groups did not immediately associate with an LMT.

The risk categorization was necessary to specify the types of risk discussed and link the type of risk to areas and processes to address and mitigate risks, e.g. policy processes, or improving education and communication for societal acceptance. Different stakeholders can identify an entirely different set of risks, co-benefits, or trade-offs based on their needs or relation to the LMT. For instance, to land use managers policy risks may constitute insufficient policy incentives to appropriately support an LMT. Meanwhile a policy maker might understand policy risks as insufficient institutional coordination to implement an LMT policy. Identifying and analyzing different categories of risks allows for the development of more effective risk management strategies that consider the potential impacts of risks on different stakeholder groups and the environment. Finally, the categorization helped to structure the analysis, and make relevant data more visible to modelers.

We followed a similar structure to LANDMARC *D6.1 Literature review of LMT potential* for categorizing and analyzing the different LMTs. The main categorization can be found in Table 2. Following new insights from stakeholders, a few adaptations were made to the LMT categorization:

Dry-seeded rice was expanded to ‘Rice management’, and cropland management was re-categorized. Peatland/wetland management was further defined to provide additional context.

The selection of LMTs is based on the case study countries in LANDMARC, and those techniques and practices that were found to be most likely to be of high impact for a local, national, continental, and global portfolio.

Category	LMT	Description	Emission reduction	CO2 removal	Main co-benefits	Main trade-offs
Agriculture	Agroforestry	Trees are deliberately combined with crops and/or animals on the same unit of land		*	Higher soil functionality; Higher system productivity	Increased labour requirement Lower yield of main crop
	Dry seeded rice – no till	Rice seeds are sown directly in the fields, by directly drilling the soil, instead of transplanting of seedlings.	*	*	Increasing soil functions, less water and labour	High weed pressure
	Reduced tillage	A decrease in disturbance to soil during crop cultivation, by reducing inversion tillage.	*	*	Lower fuel requirement	Higher pest pressure
	Integrated soil fertility management	Farming method that maximizes the agronomic efficiency of nutrients by using combination of chemical fertilizer, organic residue inputs and improved germplasm.	*		Higher yields; More efficient nutrient cycling	Sourcing of external inputs in competition with other land
	Organic agriculture	An agricultural practice in which organic materials such as animal manures, compost, leguminous plants are applied and avoiding mineral fertilizer application.	*	*	More efficient nutrient cycling Less inputs	Lower yields (10-30%)
	Biochar	Organic material made by burning biomass in a pyrolysis process, a high temperature (above 300 °C) and without oxygen, which can be used to improve soil functions and to reduce GHG emission reduction.	*	*	Increase soil pH in acidic soils Improves soil structure	High cost
Forestry	Afforestation / reforestation	Afforestation: Establishing forest by planting new trees where there was previously no tree cover. Reforestation: Replanting trees in an area where there was previously forest.		*	Habitat creation for biodiversity Watershed protection	Land use competition
	Forest management	Process of planning and implementing practices for the use of forests to meet specific environmental, economic, social, and cultural objectives.		*		
	Forest fire management	Mixture of indigenous fire management and prescribed burning method to suppress and prevent large and uncontrollable forest fires.	*			
Bioenergy	Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS)	Energy is generated from biomass and the emitted carbon dioxide is subsequently captured and stored in geological formations.		*		
Biogenic waste management	Anaerobic fermentation of manures (biogas/compost)	Process of using animal manure, and agricultural or food waste to produce methane as an energy source, and biogas slurry as compost.	*	*	Off grid household energy, manure	Additional labour
Other ecosystems	Peatland management	Protection, partial or full restoring (returning degrading peatland areas back to its original state) of peatlands.	*	*		

	Pasture management	Management of pasture for greater availability of grazing pastures for animals, maintaining the soil quality and conserving biodiversity.	*	*		
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Table 2. Categorization of LMTs based on LANDMARC D6.1.

2.2 Data gathering methodology

Overview of the methodology

During the process of coordinating tasks, several synergies were recognized between LANDMARC T4.1 ‘Qualitative climate risk assessment’, T4.2 ‘Modelling of the sensitivity of LMT to climate variations’, and T5.2 ‘Assessment of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs of LMTs’. As such, efforts were made to combine data gathering for these tasks to qualitatively assess climate risks as well as the risks of LMT implementation with stakeholders. There are currently no feed backs between the risk assessment in LANDMARC T4.1 & T5.2 and the modelling efforts in T4.2, however we reflected on how modelling results can be interesting for case study stakeholders in our General Assembly, which was held between March 26-31, 2023. We noted that there can be an incompatibility between spatial and temporal scales. Climatic models model outputs are at the regional level and time scales ranges are up to 2100 while case study scales are often at the plot/farm level and consider time frames up to 2030-50. There were some initial discussions on how climate risk modelling may be interesting for our regional stakeholder engagement, through the co-development of qualitative and quantitative story lines.

While the grant agreement initially suggested that we apply a Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) with stakeholders, we decided not to apply this methodology due to the diverse range of LMTs and the wider range of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs discussed. MCDA may be appropriate to assess the magnitude of risks; but researchers would also need to predefine risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs where stakeholder would then apply their ranking. This method would not be aligned with co-developing knowledge with stakeholders. Additionally, since there is a diversity of stakeholders across different contexts, comparability between MCDA would be limited. We aimed at providing more flexibility for case studies to gather data. Therefore, the analysis was based on the application of a questionnaire.

Task leads for LANDMARC T4.1, T4.2, and T5.2 jointly created a single questionnaire that served as a guideline for case study leads. Case study partners carried out interviews within their respective regions with stakeholders from a variety of backgrounds. Around 3 to 5 stakeholders were interviewed per case study country and LMT, with a total of 92 interviews (see section 2.3 for details).

Data collection and analysis took place in the following steps:

Step 1. Design of the initial risk assessment questionnaire

Leaders of the task performed an initial literature review to inform the questionnaire design. The aim was to have a design that could both capture the complexities of climatic and socioeconomic effects

of LMTs, as well as be adaptable for the different case study contexts around the world. This led to initial design of the stakeholder questionnaire. To accurately capture different perspectives from stakeholders, a stakeholder assessment and selection guidelines was also provided.

Step 2. Piloting of questionnaire

The questionnaire was presented to modelers and CS leads from the LANDMARC consortium (AGROINSIDER, BSC, JIN, TUD) to provide feedback and suggestions. Following this feedback round, the questionnaire was piloted by a selected set of case studies, Netherlands, and Indonesia, which represented different LMTs and cultural, climatic, and socio-economic contexts. This piloting helped to further sharpen the questionnaire design. The questionnaire questions for T5.2 were also presented to an AB member with expertise in vulnerable stakeholder research. During the piloting, we shifted the design for the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs section from a questionnaire to a semi-structured interview. Piloting case study leads found that this helped engage stakeholders in discussing more complex risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs within a socio-economic context. The full interview design can be found in the appendix.

Step 3. Questionnaire deployment for all case studies

The questionnaire, together with the stakeholder selection guidelines, was deployed to case study leads of the LANDMARC consortium. The aim was to conduct three to five interviews per case study country. The interviews were conducted between February 2022 to June 2022, with some case studies delivering their reports in November 2022 due to complications during the interview stage (such as difficult access to stakeholders or working around the planting and harvesting seasons).

Step 4. Coding, analysis, synthesis of the data

Task 4.1 and 5.2 leads collected the interview reports from all case study leads. Due to the high variety of case studies regarding contextual approaches, translations, and reporting differences, the Task 5.2 lead then manually coded the interviews based on a categorization of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs. The coded interviews for this task were then analyzed to identify clusters of results and gaps and to provide a qualitative overview to modeling teams.

Competing policies	Environmental effects	Political/Policy	Technical	Social	Financial	Security	S
	In terms of environmental opportunities, knowledge plays an important role in terms of the choice of species that provides an increase in biodiversity and therefore carbon storage capacity.	In terms of political and institutional aspects, pastures are abandoned, they do not have sufficient support because the benefits they bring are not contemplated. The new CAP will favour pastures, so that the owner is required to carry out certain actions, which he is already doing, but they will be better remunerated. For example, greater administrative control will be required by means of a field notebook in which the different actions carried out, such as sowing, fertilising, grazing, mowing, etc., are recorded.	As for the barriers to the application of good pasture management, we find that the management of Mediterranean pastures in large areas is complex due to the need to divide the land into fences and to rotate grazing over them, something that in many cases is not done due to the increased costs and limitations that this entails.	The social opportunities generated by proper pasture management are directly related to livestock farming, in such a way that good pasture management contributes to an increase in profitability, generating greater economic value, employment and therefore fixing the population in rural areas.	However, he points out that the investment in improving pastures by sowing improved species pays for itself in the first year, i.e. the benefit of the grassland is immediate and pays for itself in terms of increased quality and biomass production.		
				It is necessary that work in the countryside is better remunerated and socially recognised, for which it is necessary to provide products with added value. For example, the dehesa with livestock, in the case of cattle, which in itself provides little labour, if we improve the landscape and its conservation we will provide it with greater added value, which also involves selling the fact that pastures are CO2 sinks and their importance.	On the other hand, the high cost of acquiring land for Mediterranean pastures must be emphasised, which means that a very long period is needed to amortise this investment. This disadvantage means that pasture land is being used for the implementation of photovoltaic plants or the planting of woody species in intensive systems.		
With regard to the CAP, there is a lack of coordination between the different administrations, which means that the new CAP (2023-2027) in Spain is not updated for the most widespread crops currently grown.		There is a lack of political support for grassland, due to lack of awareness and knowledge, which leads to a lack of funding for grassland.	the lack of knowledge and lack of training on the part of farmers and landowners, which makes it necessary to hire specialised labour and therefore increases costs	With regard to social risks, there is a lack of generational change, the new generations do not want to work in the countryside. There is also a lack of knowledge about pasture cultivation, as society does not consider pasture as a crop that needs management and agronomy.	The high costs of the technology right now make it difficult to access and implement. As well as the lack of knowledge and lack of training on the part of farmers and landowners, which makes it necessary to hire specialised labour and therefore increases costs. The failure of the application of new technologies is based on the high costs of both equipment and specialised labour for their application, which is necessary due to the lack of knowledge on the part of landowners about the use of such equipment.	There is a lot of uncertainty in the income regime, there is a popular saying: "Any business that depends on the sky, is not a business", it reflects the reality of the Extremadura countryside.	
		Bureaucracy is also long and tedious in Extremadura, which hinders the development of new techniques and knowledge in general.	Lack of knowledge and awareness of the benefits of grassland: reduced erosion, increased biodiversity, increased organic matter and therefore increased carbon assimilation and storage capacity.		In the new CAP there are three new lines related to pasture: low carbon agriculture, which has achieved with spontaneous or sown biodiversity plant cover, agroecology, favouring the biodiversity of agroecosystems, and crop rotation. Payments in the new CAP for pastures are 60-70€/ha, i.e. they are very little valued in Spain.	In terms of environmental risks, a pasture plot, with optimal vegetation cover, considerably reduces soil erosion, as well as reducing emissions compared to bare soil. The opportunities generated by a pasture cover increase biodiversity and improve water and soil management.	
					From a financial point of view, it currently takes between 300-400 €/ha to establish one hectare of grassland. High capital costs are needed due to very high land prices, as well as a long payback period.		

Figure 1. Example of interview coding showing risks (red), co-benefits (green), and contextual remarks (grey).

The interviews were coded in a table. The first round of coding was done per case study grouping. Coding results were then analysed and groups per LMT and category (see Figure 1). Stakeholders were kept anonymous using unique identifiers.

The data was then analysed per LMT. The initial categorizations (see Table 1. Categorization of contextual factors for risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs for implementing LMTs based on North (1990).

Modeling teams were asked to reflect on the clustered results, identifying how their model might, or might not, incorporate the results from stakeholders in their scenario and modeling design. During an early meeting on the interview results and presentation of the current coding and clustering, modeling teams expressed their preference for a bullet style format, which was easier to understand and process for further analysis. The decision was made to keep the presentation of the coded results as such. Task leads added a more readable overview of the results for non-modelling teams.

The description of the various LMTs was summarized from LANDMARC D6.1 where available. Task leads also linked the results to the outcomes of D6.1, summarizing the results from the literature

review in D6.1 and identifying the similarities and differences from the continental stakeholder literature review with our national stakeholder engagement efforts.

Finally, it should be noted that environmental risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs (i.e. climatic risk) were not included in this deliverable. These are included in D4.1 *Climate risk assessment and risk management plan*, and as the dataset is composed of the same interviews for both deliverables, the decision was made to not replicate their work. The T4.1 lead was invited as a main reviewer, and to add their reflection on the work which was included within section 5.

Limitations of the methodology

We observed a few limitations to our methodology. First, the shift from a questionnaire to a more semi-structured interview approach is indicative for our choice of quality over quantity outputs. Case study leads indicated that to capture the stakeholder understanding risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs other than climate benefits (D4.1), a less structured approach works better. While we collected over 90 interviews on LMTs, the distribution of interviews across LMTs is not even. For example, some LMTs are arguably a more niche specialized technique, such as wildfire management, and were only represented by a single case study partner. Similarly, while we tried emphasizing a varied set of stakeholder backgrounds, we noted that particularly land-users are underrepresented such as female land use managers.

Second, the interviews were performed across a wide range of cultural contexts and translated to and from a variety of languages. We encouraged case study leads to make the interview structure 'fit' for specific stakeholders, as well as ensure that the line of questioning was appropriate both culturally, language wise, and set to engage the stakeholders first, and capture 'information that fit' later. This was done to both fully capture the stakeholders' perspective, as well ensure success for future stakeholder engagement. Translating to and from different languages and adapting to local contexts also means that the interviews (and their results) were not identical across LANDMARC. Case study leads were instrumental in providing the reports and interpreting the interviews to provide valuable data for analysis.

Third, we noted that some aspects of the semi-structured interview had a very low response rate. Stakeholders were reluctant to talk beyond their expertise, and thus discussion on an LMT portfolio rather than a singular LMT did not work at times. Furthermore, questions about mid- and long-term future implications of an LMT portfolio or the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs associated therein mostly went unanswered. While long-term benefits and risks are occasionally mentioned, the mid-term timeframe (beyond 20 years, below 70 years) was difficult to discuss. Similarly, stakeholders mentioned risks far more often than co-benefits, and rarely mentioned trade-offs. Partially this can be related to that environmental risks and co-benefits are covered by D4.1 and were not replicated here. Even then the risks outweighed other factors. Additionally, trade-offs require knowledge, information, and data to understand the interaction between different risks and co-benefits and are difficult to assess due their complexity.

2.3 Data gathering results

2.3.1 Data collection

Data was collected by the various case study teams of the LANDMARC consortium. The results shown in this section are based on the responses gathered from a total of 92 interviews from stakeholders in 13 countries including Canada, Burkina Faso, China, Spain, Kenya, Netherlands, Nepal, Portugal, Sweden, Vietnam, Germany and Venezuela. The number of interviews per country are shown in Table 3. and Table 4 below:

Country	Number of Interviews
Canada	10
Burkina Faso	5
China	9
Spain	11
Kenya	11
Netherlands	4
Nepal	4
Portugal	8
Sweden	10
Venezuela	5
Vietnam	6
Indonesia	7
Germany	2
Total	92

Table 3. Number of interviews per LANDMARC case study country.

The interviews were performed with a variety of experts, land-users, policy makers, and other stakeholders. While there is some overlap, the stated expertise or focus of the interviews is shown in the distribution in Table 4. Higher numbers of interviews, for instance in the case of agroforestry, is likely due to its prevalence in LMT portfolios in LANDMARC case study countries.

LMT	Number of Interviews
Agroforestry	33
Cropland Management - Dry Seeded Rice	3
Cropland Management	9
Biochar	19
Afforestation/ Reforestation	20
Forest Management	8
BECCS	9
Wetland Management	27
Pasture Management	18
Integrated Fire Management	2

Table 4. Number of interviews where the specified LMT was the main focus.

3. Risks, co-benefits and trade-offs of LMTs from stakeholders' perspectives

This section presents an overview of the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs of LMTs from stakeholders' perspectives. It is organized by LMT, following the categorization of LANDMARC deliverable 6.1, so as to be consistent with earlier results.

We have summarized the main findings using a heatmapping approach (see Table 5) for a quick overview of the main findings. A heatmap can provide a visualization of 'hotspots' in data and where there is a higher concentration of data points. In our research a colour code is provided to emphasise the number of risks mentioned across a risk category.

LMT	Competing Policies	Policies	Technical	Financial	Social	Security	Co-Benefits	Tradeoffs
Agroforestry	Yellow	Orange	Orange	Red	Orange	Yellow	Green	Light Brown
Dry Seeded Rice	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	White	Light Brown	White
Organic Agriculture	Orange	Red	Red	Orange	Red	Yellow	Green	Light Brown
ISFM	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Light Brown	White
Biochar	White	Yellow	Red	Orange	Yellow	White	Light Brown	Light Brown
Afforestation/ Reforestation	Yellow	Orange	Orange	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Light Green	Light Brown
Forest Management	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Light Brown	White
BECCS	Yellow	White	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Light Brown	Light Brown
Wetland Management	Yellow	Orange	Red	Red	Yellow	White	Light Brown	Light Brown
Pasture Management	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Orange	Red	Yellow	Light Brown	Light Brown
Integrated Fire Management	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	White	White	Light Brown	White

Table 5. Heatmap of stakeholder perceptions of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs for LANDMARC LMTs. Lighter colors represent less mentions. Risks have been colored yellow to red, while co-benefits and trade-offs have been colored light brown to green. A blank cell means no results.

Every mention of a risk in an interview with the representative of a country was noted as a numerical value based on the number of mentions. This number was then added to the number of main points in the description of stakeholders' perceptions of risks for each LMT. The resulting number was then

mapped across a table corresponding to the categorization of competing policies, technical aspects, financial aspects, social aspects, and security aspects for each LMT. The used shades consist of three primary colors: red, yellow and green. Values up to 15 are marked in yellow to signify a lower threshold of risks, values 15 and over are marked a deeper shade of yellow to note higher mentions. Noteworthy risks with values over 20 are marked in red, with the most significant barriers marked in the deeper shade of red. The same methodology is applied to co-benefits and trade-offs with the primary colour as green.

We have used the same approach to propose a further analysis for each portfolio, which can be found in section 6.2.

Each LMT below, starting with agroforestry, is set up as follows:

1. A short introduction to the individual LMT, including a summary of LANDMARC D6.1 *Literature review of LMT potential*, and an overview of the results for that LMT.
2. The stakeholders' perception of risks.
3. The stakeholders' perception of co-benefits.
4. The stakeholders' perception of trade-offs.
5. Gaps identified by stakeholders.

3.1 Agroforestry

Agroforestry is the integration of trees with agricultural crops on the same unit of land (Mosquera-Losada *et al.*, 2009). In the past four decades, agroforestry has gained the substantial interest of national and industry stakeholders as a land-use strategy for biological carbon (C) sequestration and GHG emissions reduction (Nair, 2014). Agroforestry also improves biodiversity and reduces soil erosion as well as boosting the economic benefit of agriculture by diversifying product range.

Summary of LMT literature review LANDMARC D6.1

Agroforestry shows immense potential for land-based mitigation potential. There is an estimated 1.1 to 2.2 Pg of atmospheric carbon that could be stored in a 50-year period of implementation (Sheppard *et al.*, 2020). It is seen to be economically viable in Europe but has an especially large potential in North America. In the USA alone the potential is estimated at 548,400 Gg C yr⁻¹. Not much data could be found for specific sequestration rates in Asia and Australia. Studies found that the economic potential of agroforestry strongly depended on the type of agroforestry, the region, and other contextual factors.

One major aspect to agroforestry are the co-benefits that might or might not be used to monetize ecosystem services that agroforestry provides. Examples are increased soil organic matter, water retention, pollination, biodiversity, and erosion reduction. Socio-cultural barriers to agroforestry include the limited access of resources and land-use given to women and minority groups which can affect the adoption of agroforestry (Borelli *et al.*, 2019). Technological barriers pertain to mostly a lack of knowledge and application of agroforestry practices.

Overview of stakeholders' perception of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs

Multiple interviews reported a refusal from farmers to adopt new and sustainable measures due to reliance on traditional methods. Furthermore, current policies are inadequate with complex bureaucracy and lack of local capacity are limiting factors to implementation of agroforestry. Multiple stakeholders also stated their reluctance to adopt agroforestry due to the high initial costs, long implementation time and low return on investment. Another barrier is a lack of technical knowledge for upscaling and implementation on the rural level, along with a lack of co-financing from the private sector. Additionally, clashes over ownership of the land are common and policies need to be better understood to facilitate adoption.

Comparison of literature review and stakeholders' responses

A lack of technological knowledge for application of agroforestry practices were mentioned by both stakeholders and literature. Limited access to land-use was cited in both the interviews and the literature; but the interviewees delved into factors such as clashes with the government over the ownership of land whereas the literature highlighted social barriers such as an inequality meted out towards women and minority groups regarding land-use and ownership. A lack of incentives to monetize ecosystem services was also noted in the literature, while the stakeholders mentioned implementation difficulties in related to high initial costs and long running time.

3.1.1 Stakeholders' perception of risks

Competing policies

- Legal pluralism between local culture/customs and national government – who owns the land, and who owns the agroforestry system? Which set of rules to apply can determine feasibility of implementation. [BF4] [VN3]
- There is a lack of coordination between institutions to support agroforestry. [NP4] [VN5]
 - o Farmers are not incentivized, and there is strong and complex regulations making the sale/removal of trees more difficult. [NP] [NL1]
 - o As it is situated between agriculture and forestry, it can be unclear who bears responsibility between institutions. [KE3]
- Current policies promote traditional crops and practices rather than sustainable alternatives. [VE1]

Policies

- The overall (long-term) political strategy is missing or lacking, or a lack of continuity between strategies. [NP4] [VE3]
 - o There is no focus on maintaining established and future sites. Rather, there is a focus on 'more agroforestry'. [KE2]
- There is a lack of capacity of local institutions to support agroforestry. [NP4] [VN5][VE1]
 - o Local institutions are not mobilized or do not have the proper resources, or mechanisms are focused on the wrong implementation level (national, rather than regional or local). [NP][VN]
 - o There is lack of knowledge (or interest) at national level on what is done at local scale or in rural areas. [VE3] [ES11]
 - o There is a lack of knowledge on how to implement and scale up agroforestry. [VN5]
 - o A lack of political support for the private sector implementing agroforestry. [NP4]
 - o Centralization of policies at the national level can lead to increased complexity and time needed to implement techniques. [VE3]
- Access to financial support for implementing agroforestry is difficult due to bureaucracy. [VN2]
- Areas/regions where smallholders are the majority of landowners are difficult to target with policies, as the small footprints are economically not interesting with regards to agroforestry. [VN4]
- There is not a formal definition for agroforestry, therefore creating policies on the topic is very difficult [NL]
- Policies are too rigid, or bureaucracy too complex, hindering implementation.
 - o Policies geared towards 'extreme ecological conservation' hinder traditional farm use and techniques. [ES11]

Technical

- There is a lack of knowledge in general population, hindering large scale adoption. [KE2] [VN5]
- Access to high quality, local seeds for tree species are not available for large scale adoption. [KE3]
- There is an uneven distribution of knowledge. Remote areas lack access to resources/education (in sustainability techniques). [KE3]
 - o Technical personnel is still trained in non-sustainable agricultural techniques. [VE1]
- A lack of (access to) machinery that can deal with mixed croplands, lack of seedling of trees suitable for agroforestry in the local conditions . [NL1]
- A general lack of knowledge of how to implement and maintain the complex agroforestry systems. [KE3]
 - o Especially in how to scale these techniques up to large scale. [KE3] [VN2]
- There is not much available area to implement the technique. [PT3]

Financial

- A lack of co-financing or return on investment is a threat to permanence. [VE3]
 - o Investments should come from private sector, government, banks. [VE4]
 - o Market changes have driven uptake of different crops/techniques. [VN2]
- While agroforestry offers a huge potential for carbon sequestration, this is not relevant for local/individual farmers. [KE3]
- Rural areas lack access to resources and markets that would support implementation. [VN2]
- There is a lack of knowledge on the market implementation of the technique. [VN3]
 - o Traditional knowledge on agroforestry is not connected to the market/value chains. [VN5]
- There is a challenge to not only have the capital to implement the technique, but also to maintain it. [KE3] [VN5]
 - o Even during good production, increased costs for agroforestry can lead to a lack of capital to maintain the system. [VN5]
- Agroforestry systems have an initial period of reduced economic returns, high implementation cost, high risk, and a long running time. [KE2] [NL1] [NP4] [VN2] [VN3] [VN4] [ES11] [PT1] [PT4]
 - o Subsidies and technical support are required to overcome initial period of investment. [KE2] [NP4] [VN2] [PT1]
 - o There is a scarcity of successful agroforestry experiences. [NL1]
 - o Reluctance to change their business models, often held for generations. [NL and more]
 - o Uncertainty about new compensation mechanisms [NL]
 - o Financial risky situations lead to a lack of investments needed to implement/maintain technique. [ES11]

- International subsidies/investments driving uptake of agroforestry might end. [VE3]

Social

- A lack of coordination across involved stakeholders. [VN2] [VE5]
- Decision-making on land use in farming environments relies on older generations, generally less open to new land management ideas than younger generations [NL]
- Regions where the inclusion of trees in farming systems is not traditional are less likely to adopt agroforestry than regions where trees were somewhat included (i.e. integrating some walnut trees because cattle likes it, as traditionally done in some parts of the Netherlands)[NL]
- Farmers are locked in to current agricultural ways, and are reluctant to adopt agroforestry. [KE3] [VN2] [VN5] [VE3] [VE5]
 - o Some may be reluctant to change the 'look of the land'. [NL1]
 - o Farmers might believe that agroforestry systems are not a viable alternative. [VE4] [VE5]
- There is a shortage of (young) labor for implementing the techniques. [VN4] [ES11]

Security

- Political conflicts can hinder implementation as they create uncertainty.
 - o Russia Ukraine war. [PT1]

3.1.2 Stakeholders' perceived co-benefits

Environmental

- Past agricultural culture has been based on external (non-local) techniques. Implementation of agroforestry goes hand in hand with promoting native species.
 - o Domestication of native species and agroforestry helps align the implementation of agroforestry with biodiversity goals. [VE4]
 - o This will also increase resilience to local climate conditions/ [VE4]

Policies

- Local institutional support and knowledge can aid in selecting the right producers, land, and species. [VE3]
- There is strong political support to increase agroforestry, translating to implementation opportunities.
 - o The government aims for the diversification of cropping systems. [VN4]
 - o Legal frameworks are set in place to support the implementation. [VE3]
- International conventions, programs, and treaties are pushing for national support to implement agroforestry.
 - o National institutions are created and designed to support international push. [VE3]

Technical

- Existing farm technologies and practices support implementation in this area. [VN3]
- Farmers have strong knowledge on local conservation/agroforestry techniques. [PT2]
- Higher input prices for conventional agriculture (fertilizers) are driving support for alternative farming methods. [VN3] [VE1]

Social

- Quality of life for people working in agroforestry systems is increased. [KE2]
 - o Reduced exposition to pesticides. [KE2]
- Promoting agroforestry techniques helps preserve traditional knowledge. [VE4]
- Agroforestry provides opportunities for improving distribution of tasks within households (eg firewood gathering by women). [KE3]
- There is a widespread rejection of ideas coming from the environmental sector within the farming community stemming from recent regulations in nitrogen limits. Organic and conventional farming are two parallel sectors with little interaction [NL]

Financial

- Carbon pledge by private sector might drive agroforestry. [VN3] [VN4]
- Agroforestry can drive new sources of income for the region, such as tourism and ecosystem services activities. [PT2]

Security

- Agroforestry helps protect the soil against soil erosion and landslides. [KE3]

3.1.3 Stakeholders' perceived trade-offs

Policies

- How land is designated (with the government) can determine the constraints of its use for land users.
 - o Once land is designated as forest, it can no longer be used for agriculture. [NL1]
 - o Environmental targets can clash with agricultural targets. [VE4] [VE5]

Financial

- Consumers need to drive uptake of non-conventional agricultural systems, but this will cost more. [VE5]

Security

- Agroforestry techniques cannot scale up to provide sufficient food production at macro scale. [VE1]

3.1.4 Gaps observed based on stakeholder insights

Stakeholder

- Mechanism/platform needed to coordinate multiple stakeholders in the value chain, including public sector, private sector, NGOs, IDH, etc. [VN5] [BF4]
- Policies must be revised and suited to reach local communities in attaining sustainability and mitigation goals.
 - o National policies must fit cultural aspects. [VE4]
- National environmental accountability/monitoring system is needed. [VE5]
 - o No monitoring system exists to properly account for co-benefits of agroforestry, for instance macrofungal biodiversity, quality of life for farmers, health benefits. [BF4]
- There is lack of suitability studies for different agroforestry practices, species, and suitability at local scale. [NP4]

Temporal

- A long term perspective is required on farming techniques and investment/return. [KE2]
- Most challenges are related to the long lead up time for the environmental and financial benefits of agroforestry. [NL1] [VN3] [VE1]

3.2 Cropland Management: Rice management

Improved rice management involves changing seeding practices, using different seedlings, or other management techniques. A major case study focus was dry seeded rice, which involves the sowing of rice seeds directly into the fields, via drilling or broadcasting which is different from the traditional rice farming practice of transplanting seedlings grown in the nursery into the fields. Direct planting eliminates costs associated with land preparation, transportation, and nurseries. Dry seeded rice can therefore reduce methane emissions and sequester carbon by utilizing no tillage technology.

Summary of LMT literature review LANDMARC D6.1

Dry seeded rice is estimated to have a global mitigation potential of 217 MtCO₂e per year (Ahmed, Almeida and Aminetzah, 2020). Most production takes place in Asia, followed by Africa. Methane emissions can be cut down drastically with dry seeded rice, with methane emissions from dry seeded rice at 0.6 to 4.9 kg per hectare compared to a conventional rice field at 42.4 to 57.8 kg per hectare (Bhatia *et al.*, 2013). Dry seeded rice practices are applicable for farmers with low resources as it was found to reduce labor requirements by 66% (Laing *et al.*, 2018). However, the availability of seed drills and machinery required is a major financial barrier to the implementation. Policy reforms are also required to enable ownership of these machines by farmers. Current rice varieties may not be suitable for dry seeded rice (Farooq *et al.*, 2011). Direct seeding methods may also pose a threat to the traditional beliefs of farmers and dissuade them from adopting dry seeded rice. There is a general lack of knowledge concerning the machinery required for dry seeded rice and as such this poses a barrier to adoption and implementation.

Overview of stakeholders' perception of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs

Interviewees reported an inadequate knowledge base. Long-term unprofitability and commitment were considered limiting factors to implementation. As with agroforestry, there is a reluctance to adopt new measures and changing existing practices to new management techniques such as dry seeded rice.

Comparison of literature review and stakeholders' responses

There is a lack of supporting policies that enable ownership of machinery by farmers and financial support and subsidies which is mentioned in both the literature and the stakeholder interviews. A lack of technical knowledge concerning implementation, management and running of machinery is also highlighted in both cases. The stakeholder interviews indicate a lack of institutional capacity at the local level, which is a significant barrier. Although the literature suggests that dry seeded rice is great for farmers with low resources, the interviewees mention that it is not economically feasible for them to change farming practices due to of limited knowledge and capacity for implementation.

3.2.1 Stakeholders' perception of risks

Competing policies

- The overall national objective is to increase (traditional) agricultural production. [NP1]

- There is a lack of coordination between institutions on implementing sustainable policies. [NP1]

Policies

- Alternative rice cropland management needs continued support and subsidies. There is a lack of commitment from local and provincial governments. [NP1]
 - o Long term commitment is lacking. After completion of pilot projects, no further support is offered, leading to lack of widespread adoption. [NP2]

Technical

- Institutional capacity to support implementation is lacking, especially at provincial and local level. [NP2]
- A lack of detailed local knowledge has led to implementing the wrong techniques, resulting in project and adoption failure. [NP1]
 - o Technological blind spots are a risk, as the wrong techniques are promoted. [NP1]

Social

- Farmers are locked in to current agricultural techniques and are reluctant to change.
- Initial failure of technique (crop failures) can lead to discarding the technique for long-term use. [NP1]

Financial

- Changing farming practices presents an economic risk for those involved if there is no adequate knowledge. [NP1]
- Increased costs of input for farmers and decreased rice profits meant that rice production is not a profitable crop. [NP2]

3.2.2 Stakeholders' perceived co-benefits

- Positive synergies with national GHG targets. [NP1]

3.2.3 Stakeholders' perceived trade-offs

No trade-offs were noted during the interviews.

3.2.4 Gaps observed based on stakeholder insights

Several stakeholders noted that the LMT should be expanded towards rice management in general, rather than a specific rice management application. The portfolio has since been adjusted.

3.3 Cropland management: Integrated soil fertility management

Integrated soil fertility management (ISFM) is the combination of several inputs to maximize the agronomic use efficiency of nutrients. This includes the use of fertilizer, organic residue inputs and improved germplasm (Vanlauwe *et al.*, 2010). This application leads to a significant increase in carbon inputs into the soil which in turn leads to greater yield and buildup of SOC, making ISFM a suitable carbon dioxide removal technology.

Summary of LMT literature review LANDMARC D6.1

When applied to soils in Africa, it was found that ISFM would abate about 12.5 mln t CO₂ in a 40 year period (Bryan *et al.*, 2013). However, ISFM may not be able to sequester CO₂ in soils that are at the start of cultivation. A meta-analysis about ISFM showed that the SOC losses were 0.13 t C (0.48 t CO₂) and 0.78 t C (2.86 t CO₂) per ha per year lower compared to standard practices) (Kihara *et al.*, 2020). A modelling study concluded that ISFM adoption would increase the GDP of a nation, without the need to pay for carbon sequestration. There may be a reluctance to deviate from traditional practices, especially in sub-Saharan Africa. There is a lack of knowledge about soil fertility too, which is a crucial aspect of ISFM. Lack of capital and insufficient availability of mineral fertilizer are noticeable constraints on the adoption of ISFM.

ISFM is a promising technology to mitigate GHG for its potential for reduced emissions compared to traditional practices and the increased yield that ISFM provides. However, there is a significant lack of knowledge about the mitigation potential on a large scale and the subsequent overall costs for emissions reduction.

Overview of stakeholders' perception of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs

Interviews note the lack of knowledge for implementation of ISFM and current policy measures are unsuitable. Positive policy measures are further hindered by lobbying for alternative policies. The logistics in implementation of ISFM are complex, and there is resistance amongst landowners to adapt their practices. Social factors such as targeting the same set of farmers as primary stakeholders rather than diversifying might also contribute to limited implementation. There is a lack of technical knowledge at the national level and financial risks associated are also to be noted. Lack of financing is a major limiting factor along with labor-intensive implementation and inadequate management. However, the crops produced through ISFM are more resilient which is an important advantage, especially noted in areas under high threat of climatic changes.

Comparison of literature review and stakeholders' responses

The literature on ISFM suggests that it is an excellent carbon dioxide removal technology, with great sequestration rates and economic benefits. However, in practice, there is a reluctance to adopt ISFM and preference to stick to traditional farming practices owing to a lack of technical knowledge and resources which is mentioned in both the interviews and the available literature. Current policy

measures were also deemed unsuitable by the stakeholders, with the added problem of limited financing coupled with labor-intensive implementation.

3.3.1 Stakeholders' perception of risks

Competing policies

- Lobbying for alternative policies that do not support ISFM. [KE10]
 - o Fertilizer companies lobby for conventional agricultural techniques. [KE10]
- There is a lack of coordination between institutions to support ISFM. [KE6]
 - o As it is situated between waste management and agriculture, it can be unclear who is bears responsibility between institutions. [KE6]

Policies

- Policies have increased costs for implementation of the technique. [KE7]
 - o Higher fuel prices have led to reduced access to inputs, markets. [KE7]
- Lack of policy incentives for implementation. [KE7]
- Agricultural policies target large scale farmers, rather than smallholders for whom ISFM is more beneficial. [KE7]

Technical

- A lack of implementation knowledge at national/government level. [KE7] [KE10]
 - o Farmers receive less support. [KE7]
 - o Adverse laws with unintended consequences for implementation of ISFM. [KE10]
- A lack of implementation knowledge among land-users. [KE6]
 - o Lack of education amongst land-users is a barrier to large-scale adoption. [KE7]
- Logistics of implementation can be difficult. [KE6] [KE10]
 - o New areas for implementation are hard to reach/have reduced access to markets.

Social

- There is a threat of 'stakeholder lock-in', selecting the same set of farmers rather than targeting widespread adoption. [KE7]
- Corruption. [KE7]
- Patriarchal society, while implementation is done by women. [KE10]
 - o Those responsible for investment not responsible for implementation. [KE10]
 - o Women often cannot attend training. [KE10]
- Poor farmers do not have access/cannot maintain resources. [KE10]

Financial

- The technique has high implementation costs. [KE6] [KE10]
 - o Labor intensive to implement when compared to conventional agriculture. [KE6] [KE10]

○

Security

- Delayed consequences of good/bad management has led to adoption of 'easier' techniques (conventional fertilizer use). [KE10]

3.3.2 *Stakeholders' perceived co-Benefits*

Technical

- Most farmers are aware of potential benefits but lack the financial means to make use of new techniques. [KE10]

Security

- Improved crop varieties are more resilient, reducing yield failure for farmers. [KE7]

3.3.3 *Stakeholders' perceived trade-offs*

Stakeholders noted no trade-offs in the interviews.

3.3.4 *Gaps observed based on stakeholder insights*

- There is no good knowledge platform where farmers can get high quality, neutral information for implementation of ISFM. [KE7]

3.4 Cropland management: organic agriculture

Organic agriculture is a method of farming that relies on natural processes and techniques to grow crops and raise animals, while avoiding the use of synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, and genetically modified organisms (GMOs). Organic farmers focus on building fertile soils through practices such as crop rotation, cover cropping, and composting, and they often use natural pest control methods like beneficial insects, crop diversity, and habitat management.

Overview of stakeholders' perception of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs

Interviews state major political and policy risks for the implementation of this LMT such as a misalignment between the involved institutions. Knowledge and technological gap at the local level are prevalent in the interviews. Furthermore, social factors such as the reluctance of farmers to change practices, lack of societal support, and lack of access to infrastructure combined with the unfamiliarity with new techniques are crucial barriers to be overcome. Financial challenges such as the long period between investment and returns need to be considered as well. However, social co-benefits such as reduced soil erosion and consequently, reduced risk of landslides are important positive drivers for adoption of organic culture.

Comparison of literature review and stakeholders' responses

The literature on organic agriculture indicates significant economic benefits as compared to conventional agricultural practices. Stakeholders also highlight substantial societal benefits regarding soil erosion and reduced irrigation and production costs. However, multiple stakeholder interviews indicated a lack of policy reforms and resources allocated to organic agriculture. Some common barriers mentioned by stakeholders and available literature were a lack of technical knowledge for organic farming, regulation against use of pesticides, uncertain sequestration potential, high initial investment requirements and a preference for traditional farming practices. The stakeholders also mentioned that they were unfamiliar with alternative techniques and as such lacked societal support for the initiative. They also voiced their concerns about the reliance on long-term investment and cost of machinery.

3.4.1 Stakeholders' perception of risks

Competing policies

- Policies promote conventional agriculture. [ID1] [CH2]
 - o Subsidies target short term gains over long term gains. [CH1]
 - o Subsidies for conventional agriculture. [BF2]
 - o International subsidies promote adverse techniques. [CH8]
- Strong regulations impede new techniques. [CH2]
 - o Regulations on use of pesticides. [CH2] [CH3]
- Institutional misalignment between institutions/governance scales. [ID3] [ID4] [ID6] [ID1]
 - o Strong policies but weak execution at local level. [ID3]
 - o Lack of resources at implementation scale. [ID4] [ID6]

- Lack of upwards transfer of knowledge from local level. [ID4]

Policies

- Strong lobby/preference for conventional agriculture. [CH4] [CH2] [KE5]
- Poor policy design. [ID4] [ID5] [CH3] [ID1]
- Lack of government support for land users. [BF5] [ID3]
- Lack of political support to implement technique. [CH1] [ID3] [ID4] [ID5] [ID1] [CH4]
 - Regional/municipal system makes implementation complex. [CH1] [ID3]
 - Focus on short-term profits over long-term sustainability. [CH2]
 - Lack of continuity between administrations. [ID5] [ID6] [ID1]
 - Lack of continuity from Western funding. [KE11]
- Risk of increased bureaucracy for carbon certification schemes. [CH6]
 - Small scale of landholders would impede implementation of mitigation. [CH6]
- Corruption. [ID1] [ID4]
- Large (international) investments do not reach smallholders willing to implement technique. [KE11]

Technical

- Old data impedes implementation of technique. [ID3]
- Lack of support and technology to support new techniques. [BF2] [BF5]
- Knowledge gaps of landusers on LMT. [BF5] [CH1] [CH2] [CH8]
- Path dependency of land-use. [CH1] [CH2]
 - Land might have different designated use not ideal for technique. [CH1] [PT5] [PT6]
- Access to required technology. [CH3]
 - Lack of access to (specialized) machinery. [CH8] [KE5]
 - Lack of ownership. [ID5]
 - Access to seeds. [BF2]
- Technological lock-in. [ID3]
- Infrastructure access to remote, rural areas. [ID4] [ID5] [ID6] [KE5] [BF2]
- Limited scalability. [ID3] [ID5] [ID6] [CH6]
 - Limited labour available. [ID6]
 - Limited land. [CH6]

Social

- Farmers do not like technique, have alternative uses for residuals. [BF3]
- Farmers prefer current farming practices. [ID3] [ID4] [ID6] [ID1] [BF2] [BF3]
 - Lack of familiarity with alternative technique. [BF2] [BF3] [CH7] [CH8]
- Lack of generational continuity. [BF2]
- Cultural value of traditional agriculture. [BF2]
 - Resentment of (resemblance of) colonial agriculture. [KE11]

- Lack of societal support for sustainable agriculture. [CH4] [CH6] [CH2] [CH4]
 - o Increased food costs for consumer.
- Gender inequality impedes technique implementation. [ID5] [KE11]
 - o On field implementation by women, while business and money issues through men. [KE11]
- Population pressure on land. [KE11]
- Social pressure from other farmers, as mulching and no tilling makes the field look “dirty “ and the farmer is perceived as “lazy “ [CH]

Financial

- Long investment time before returns. [CH1] [KE5] [ID6]
 - o Subsistence farmers focus on short-term. [KE5]
 - o Land tenure needs to be assured. [CH8]
- Capacity gaps. [ID5]
- Lack of financial support for technique. [CH6]
- Investment costs to implement technique. [ID6]
 - o Cost of new seeds. [BF5]
 - o Cost of machinery. [Ch7]
- Need (and cost of) for certification. [ID4]

Security

- Uncertainty of agricultural pricing.
 - o Consequences of Russia – Ukraine war. [CH3] [PT5] [PT6]
 - o Global markets driving product price. [ID5]

3.4.2 Stakeholders' perceived co-benefits

Policies

- Growing subsidies for sustainable techniques. [CH7]
- High collaboration between governments and landusers. [PT5]

Technical

- Growing networks for aiding implementation. [KE11]
- Capacity to decrease yield gaps with good management. [CH1]
- Knowledge is already present. [CH4]

Financial

- Reduced irrigation costs. [CH6]
- Reduced production costs. [CH3]
- Sustainable packing in consumer demand. [PT5]

Social

- Community support to alleviate risks. [ID3] [ID4]

Security

- Societal benefits.
 - o Reduced erosion. [CH5] [CH7] [CH8]
 - o Reduced leaching. [CH7] [CH8]
 - o Reduced landslides due to erosion. [CH5] [CH7] [CH8]
- High importance of agricultural sector for government. [PT5]
- Increased national independence. [CH4]

3.4.3 *Stakeholders' perceived trade-offs*

Technical

- Higher pest pressures. [CH6]

3.4.4 *Gaps observed based on stakeholder insights*

Stakeholders noted no gaps in the interviews.

3.5 Afforestation and reforestation

Afforestation is the process of creating forest cover in an area with no prior forest cover.

Reforestation is the process of replating trees in a previously forested area (Food and Organization, 2010). Forests act as carbon sinks and are hence important for carbon sequestration. In this regard, afforestation and reforestation help improve forest functions including ecosystem services, biodiversity and soil protection as well as reducing the vulnerability of local communities to climate change.

Summary of LMT literature review LANDMARC D6.1

Globally forest mitigation can mitigate GHG up to 102.9 GtCO₂b 035, which equals 0.6 to 5.2 GtCO₂/yr (Austin *et al.*, 2020). Afforestation is widely considered the most cost effective carbon sequestration option (IPCC, 2022). It has the greatest potential in tropical countries where tree growth rates and sequestration rates are higher than other countries (Raihan *et al.*, 2019). At moderate to high CO₂ prices, agricultural areas can be converted into forests as it is an economic alternative to agriculture at these rates (Doelman *et al.*, 2020).

Afforestation requires large amounts of land which may lead to a reduction in agricultural area. This could in effect lead to an increase in food prices which would be unfavorable. A significant portion (42%) of the maximum reforestation mitigation potential depends on a reduced need for pasture and reduced beef consumption (Griscom *et al.*, 2017). Droughts, fires, and diseases might also be unpredictable barriers to the effectiveness of afforestation. Another significant problem to afforestation/reforestation is that only about 2.5% of the climate mitigation budget is allotted to land-based sequestration efforts (Griscom *et al.*, 2017).

Overview of stakeholders' perception of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs

Interviews state that there are numerous political barriers and lack of policy incentives supporting afforestation/ reforestation. These include (a lack of) political support, slow bureaucracy, and a lack of coordination between actors. Technical know-how about scaling up is lacking in multiple countries, with major long-term uncertainties long-term about the future of carbon sequestration through afforestation. Long-term land use is considered by some stakeholders to be problematic, as there is a high degree of uncertainty regarding ownership, land leasing, and governance. This leads to technical and financial blind spots about long term investments and financial returns from afforestation. Finally, interviews note a lack of financing available for implementation. However, co-benefits such as job creation can be a strong driver, with several countries actively enabling supporting policies at the national level.

Comparison of literature review and stakeholders' responses

According to the literature, afforestation is the most cost-effective means to sequester carbon, especially in tropical countries. However, this requires a large amount of land as noted by stakeholders as well as available literature. Unpredictable events such as forest fires, droughts and land-tenure agreements are also highlighted by both sources. Stakeholders in particular mention a

lack of supporting policies and incentives as well as scarcity of resources to scale up. High initial investment and low economic benefits of the technique are also concerns voiced by the stakeholders. However, the stakeholders seem to be well informed about opportunities for job-creation and reduction of the risk of environmental degradation via the implementation of this technique.

3.5.1 Stakeholders' perception of risks

Competing policies

- Legal pluralism favouring different systems. [KE8]

Policies

- Political instability. [BF1]
 - o Restricted access to areas. [BF1]
- Lack of expertise in governing body. [KE1]
- Lack of incentives to implement technique. [KE9]
- Climate policies are isolated from other policy aspects. [KE9]
- Lack of political support at national level. [VN1]
- Slow bureaucracy. [E1]
- Risk of technology lock-in at national and local level. [VN1]
- Lack of coordination and responsibilities between implementing actors. [KE8]

Technical

- Technique permanence. [SE10]
- Technique implementation.
 - o Animals eating seeds/young trees. [KE1]
 - o Poor quality seedlings. [KE1]
 - o No resources to protect seedlings. [KE1]
- No resources to scale up. [KE1] [DE1] [VN1]
 - o Lack of seedlings at scale. [KE8][DE1]
 - o Lack of research on efficient implementation. [KE8]
 - o Lack of financial resources. [KE8]
- Mismatch between top-down and bottom-up scaling. [KE9]
 - o Mismatch of knowledge between government/experts and local implementation. [KE9]
- Lack of knowledge among land-users. [KE1]

Social

- Uncertainty about land tenure disincentives long-term techniques. [BF1] [KE8]
- Lack of resources to implement technique. [KE1]
 - o Poverty trap. [KE1]

- Cultural/traditional aversion to technique. [KE9]

Financial

- Unclear implications for insurance systems on technique failure. [SE10]
- Little support from private sector for technique. [KE9]
- Low economic benefits from technique. [VN1]
- High initial investment with long amortisation period. [ES1] [ES2]

Security

- Risk of focus on carbon offsets rather than systemic transitions. [SE10]
- Migration is driving land-use changes. [BF1]
- Technique uncertainties in long term. [SE10]
 - o Unknown demand for sequestered carbon.
 - o International regulation changes.

3.5.2 *Stakeholders' perceived co-benefits*

Policies

- Enabling policies have been enacted at national/regional level. [KE8] [KE9] [ES1] [ES2]
 - o Good political support for technique. [KE9] [ES1]
 - o Subsidies for implementation of technique. [ES1] [ES2]

Financial

- Can develop into profitable sector. [KE1]
- Carbon markets would be easy incentive for technique proliferation. [SE10]
- Subsidies would aid economic case of land with low productivity. [ES1]
- Technique promotes job creation in vulnerable areas. [ES1] [ES2]

Security

- Reduced risk of damaging events (floods). [KE1]
 - o Reduced land degradation costs and societal risks. [KE8]
 - o Reduced damage to infrastructure. [KE9]

3.5.3 *Stakeholders' perceived trade-offs*

- Alternative (agricultural, habitation) land-uses, driven by population growth. [KE8] [BF1]

3.5.4 *Gaps observed based on stakeholder insights*

Stakeholders

- Adaptation of the technique (species) is a key issue. [SE10]
 - o Focus on adaptation is needed to secure buy-in from communities. [KE9]
- Market based instruments to enhance technique adoption. [SE10]

- Vulnerable groups need to be involved more in value chain of sustainable implementation of technique. [KE8]

3.6 Forest management

Forest management is the process of process of planning and implementing practices to use forests to meet certain environmental, economic, ecological, social, and cultural objectives. Forest management can be an effective method for CO₂ removal and to increase the storage of carbon in living and dead biomass and soil. Forest management usually involves increasing forest carbon stocks, increasing resilience of forest stands and increasing carbon stock in harvested wood products. The Global Forest Resource Assessment Report (Food and Organization, 2010) states that globally, the area of managed forests, is 2.05 billion ha.

Summary of LMT literature review LANDMARC D6.1

The mitigation potential varies according to different studies and assumptions. Overall, the proper implementation could lead to an annual carbon sink of -48 Mt CO₂ in living biomass, which is a significant amount for carbon sequestration (Böttcher, 2018).

A study by the European Commission in 2021 revealed that the cost for increasing carbon stocks in forests to meet the required sink target in the EU is relatively low at about 5-10 EUR/tCO₂. Forest management can be applied over large land areas and does not require land conversion; hence it is moderate in cost. Forest management has the potential to provide co-benefits regarding biodiversity and carbon stock increases (Böttcher *et al.*, 2021). Biomass growth is also restricted severely by temperature and water limitations in the EU. Forest owners may also be biased towards timber sales and hence a policy intervention to establish pricing of ecosystem services must be prioritized (Böttcher *et al.*, 2021).

Overview of stakeholders' perception of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs

Interviews noted the lack of coordination between the involved institutions. Excessive bureaucracy results in a slow adoption of forest management practices and could hamper future implementation and expansion of practices. Furthermore, there is a lack of technical knowledge among small forest owners along with a lack of knowledge management and social awareness. The permanence of carbon stored in forests is also uncertain, which increases doubts surrounding implementation. Forest management techniques in general have low profit margins which hinders financial support in favor of this technique. However, possibilities of payments for ecosystem services other than wood sales including options such as eco-tourism resulting from forest management may prove to be strong drivers for adoption and implementation in the future.

Comparison of literature review and stakeholders' responses

The literature on forest management makes a good case for adoption by highlighting the significant mitigation potential as well as relatively low cost for increasing carbon stocks. Several co-benefits regarding biodiversity are also highlighted in the literature, while stakeholder interviews mention a possibility of financial benefits resulting from ecotourism. However, stakeholders mention a critical lack of coordination between national and regional guiding bodies which is not mentioned in the

literature. The stakeholders also shared their concerns over lack of societal awareness, low profit margin and lack of local markets in the interviews.

3.6.1 Stakeholders' perception of risks

Competing policies

- Lack of coordination between national institutions. [NP3]
 - o Institutional legacy hinders implementation. [NP3]
 - o Policies/subsidies support adverse implementation. [ES4]
- Lack of coordination between international and national/regional guidelines/ [ES3] [ES4]
 - o Local/regional administrations do not have capacity to respond to continental guidelines. [ES3]

Policies

- Corruption is a risk to implementation. [NP3]
 - o Middlemen and government officers. [NP3]
- Excessive bureaucracy to implement measures. [ES3] [ES4]
 - o Bureaucracy leading to higher implementation costs. [ES4]
- Lack of qualified staff to implement measures. [ES3]
- Implementation policies are the same for large companies as SMEs. [ES3]
 - o Policies can have adverse effects during difficult times. [ES3]
- Decentralization has led to unclear forest management. [BF1]

Technical

- Not enough seedlings available. [DE1]
- Lack of awareness by small forest users. [PT7]
- Lack of knowledge by small forest users. [PT7]
- Lack of institutional history, knowledge management for forestry techniques. [BF1]

Social

- Lack of societal awareness which could drive technique implementation. [ES3] [ES4] [PT7]
 - o Change in consumer habits is necessary to focus on local products. [ES3]
- Focus on 'extreme' conservatism, rather than improved management. [ES3]
- Rural depopulation leads to a lack of manpower and a decrease of actively managed forests. Young generations not interested in the agricultural sector.[ES]

Financial

- Local implementation by SMEs leads to low profit margins. [ES3]
- Low profit margin in forestry sector. [ES4]
 - o Devaluation of rural products. [ES4]

- Lack of local market. [ES3]
 - o Lack of demand for technologies focusing on local markets, which could drive local forest management. [ES3]
- Technique is risky due to permanence issues.
 - o Disease led to a large loss of trees and financial consequences. [NP3]
 - o Risk of forest fires.

Security

- Permanence under threat from changing conditions.
 - o Forest fires increasingly common but not a policy focus as no people are affected. [NP3]

3.6.2 *Stakeholders' perceived co-benefits*

Policies

- Strengthening forest user groups and creating good policy guidelines for technique implementation will also alleviate corruption. [NP3]

Security

- Self-sufficiency. [ES4]
- Ecotourism possibilities. [ES4]

3.6.3 *Stakeholders' perceived trade-offs*

No trade-offs were noted by stakeholders in the interviews.

3.6.4 *Gaps observed based on stakeholder insights*

Stakeholders

- Identification and recommendation of trees based on local suitability (local micro climate). [NP3]
- Research needed on capacity to help withstand landslides. [NP3]

3.7 Biochar

Biochar is an organic material synthesized through a pyrolysis process that involves the burning of biomass at high temperatures. It is primarily used to increase the carbon sequestration capacity of soils. Other benefits of biochar use are an increase in agricultural yields, increase in water storage capacity of soils, and reduction in GHG emissions.

Summary of LMT literature review LANDMARC D6.1

An early study (Woolf *et al.*, 2010) indicated that the global technical mitigation potential of biochar was about 6.6 GtC/year. Europe and North America were found to have a combined potential of 0.7 GtC/year (Pratt and Moran, 2010). However, the cost of biochar is comparatively higher in comparison to other similar measures at about 100 USD/tC (88,38EUR) in developed countries. Low GDP countries have a lower cost due to the significant positive effects of biochar on their yields (Robb and Joseph, 2019). A significant global barrier is the technological difficulty in implementing biochar standards in different regions, as the effects of implementation differ widely depending on climate, sources of biomass, and production methods (Smith *et al.*, 2016, 2019). Scaling up is often difficult as pyrolysis on a larger scale is expensive and difficult to maintain. Finally, the high cost of this LMT and the lack of supportive policy in the context of EU are major barriers.

Overview of stakeholders' perception of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs

Interviewees discussed political factors such as absence of long-term financing policy incentives and technical barriers in transportation and upscaling as major barriers. As this technique is very dependent on biomass and technology, the uncertainty surrounding procurement and quality of biomass is a significant curtailing factor as noted by stakeholders. In the financial sector, high investment costs, uncertainty about future markets and uncertain long-term profits are seen as implementation barriers as they contribute to the complexity of the business case. Social skepticism and gender inequal roles in the process may also contribute to the complexity of implementation. However, biochar has great environmental co-benefits, performance, sequestration rate and possible synergies with other LMTs which make it a promising LMT with a large potential market.

Comparison of literature review and stakeholders' responses

The relatively high cost of Biochar and a heavy reliance on technology is a barrier mentioned in the literature as well as the stakeholder interviews. Uncertainty regarding long-term investment in the technology is also noted by both sources. Additionally, available literature suggests that there may be unpredictable uncertainties related to biochar-soil interaction which could be a significant cause of concern. The technological difficulties in the implementation of this technique is highlighted by stakeholders in accordance with the literature. Difficulties in scaling up, lack of trained personnel and lack of knowledge at municipal levels are also indicated through the stakeholder interviews. According to the stakeholders, biomass competition can lead to feedstock shortage, which is a problem not distinctly mentioned in the literature, which focuses more on soil biochemistry.

Stakeholders are also concerned about the long-term effectiveness and investment related to Biochar, as it presents a complex business case with multiple factors that need to succeed.

3.7.1 Stakeholders' perception of risks

Policies

- Adverse policies hinder implementation of technology. [CA1]
- Financial policy incentives are needed to grow the initial market. [SE1] [SE7]
- Initial state run support systems are required but need to be phased out. [SE7]
- Lack of clear long-term policies and financing hinder implementation. [SE2]

Technical

- Biomass competition could lead to feedstock shortage. [CA1] [SE1]
- Contaminated biochar could find its way to the markets [CA1]
- Small scale implementation is more harmful than beneficial due to loss of secondary benefits. [CA1]
- Source of biomass for feedstock can be problematic. [SE1] [KE4]
 - o Can lead to monocultures to maintain growth of market. [SE1]
- Consistent carbon accounting is a problem. [SE6]
 - o Additionality is a problem. [SE6]
- Storage and transportation are a problem, especially when upscaling. [SE7] [SE3]
- Long lead-in times for establishing LMT facilities. [SE1] [SE5] [SE2]
- Long-term effectiveness of biochar is unknown. [SE1] [SE3]
- Lack of knowledge at municipal level. [SE2] [SE5]

Financial

- Lack of protocols and guidelines lead to uncertain investment climate. [SE2]
- Large ETS markets are required for long-term feasibility. [SE7] [SE1]
 - o Low ETS pricing. [CH5]
- High investment, operational costs. [SE1] [SE7] [SE3] [SE5]
 - o Uncertainty in financing. [SE2] [SE3]
- Complex business case with multiple components that are needed to be successful. [SE1] [SE2] [SE3] [SE5] [SE7]

Social

- Skepticism among policymakers, land-users. [CH5]
- Lack of access to value-chain by groups of stakeholders. [KE4]
 - o E.G. feedstock products managed by women who do not have access to market tools. [KE4]
 - o Technique success might take away the implementation from women. [KE4]
 - o Investments target large-scale projects. [KE4]

3.7.2 *Stakeholders' perceived co-benefits*

Technical

- Biochar has lowest climate related risks of available/likely LMTs. [CH5]
 - o Good permanence.
 - o Biochar CO2 sequestration certificates in high demand due to permanence. [CH5]
- Good knock-on benefits, ie change in cooking materials leading to better air quality. [KE4]
- Some technologies can be connected to existing energy infrastructure. [CA1]
- Local lead-in times are shorter as many pre-requisites already exist. [SE1]
- Applicable at many scales, in many settings (eg rural farmers, cities). [SE1]
 - o Can be utilized in many settings, globally. [SE1]
- Synergies with other LMTs, e.g. forest management and reforestation. [CH5] [KE4]

Financial

- There is large societal potential for a biochar market. [SE6]
- Low risk markets will likely develop. [SE7]

3.7.3 *Stakeholders' perceived trade-offs*

- Long lead-in times lead to lock-in of land-use. [SE5]

3.7.4 *Gaps observed based on stakeholder insights*

Stakeholder

- Standardization is needed.
- Research in BECCS and biochar is a necessity for further implementation. [SE3] [SE6]
- LMT regulations need to be locally adapted. [SE5]

3.8 Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage

Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) is a process consisting of the removal of CO₂ from atmosphere and oceans, whereafter the energy is harvested through conversion and the carbon is stored under the ground (Friedmann et al., 2020). The main advantage of BECCS lies in its ability to produce energy while simultaneously offsetting carbon emissions.

Summary of LMT literature review LANDMARC D6.1

Globally, BECCS is estimated to have a NET potential of 0.5-5 GtCO₂/year which accounts for 3-8% of total energy consumption (Canadell and Schulze, 2014; Fuss *et al.*, 2018). The economic potential of BECCS is dependent on the region where it is being implemented. Globally it is estimated that BECCS could have a cost of 100-200 USD/tCO₂ (88.41-177.11 EUR) (Fuss *et al.*, 2018).

Given that BECCS is a new technology, the socio-cultural barriers of BECCS are still not well researched. However, it is expected its implementation will increase land competition for food, housing, and other resources. Monitoring and long-term storage of CO₂ are also issues to be considered before implementation. Further studies are necessary to optimize the implementation of BECCS, including studies into the proper accounting of land suitable for bioenergy production, underground storage facilities, as well as the environmental impact of BECCS on biodiversity, air pollution and waste generation. Further research is needed at the regional level to consider food security, clean energy, and water resources. There are also insufficient policies supporting large scale deployment of BECCS. In Latin America, a large gap persists with regards to transportation and storage infrastructure. Societal support at a local level plays a huge role in the implementation of BECCS and this technology is more widely accepted in high-income countries. Converting land to forests for carbon sinks could result in land grabs and human rights violations which are potential barriers.

Overview of stakeholders' perception of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs

The high technical complexity in the implementation of BECCS, along with limited access to biomass restricts a current positive outlook on the technology. This is worsened by a lack of technical knowledge about the process amongst key stakeholders. Furthermore, uncertainty about profitability and long-term dependence on the technology once implemented are clear barriers to implementation, as large investments may not be wise if a better alternative to BECCS appears in the near future. Emerging economies with prevalent land-use conflicts are especially vulnerable to long-term uncertainty. However, forest owners are becoming increasingly interested in BECCS as it has several positive financial co-benefits resulting from an increased forest carbon sequestration.

Comparison of literature review and stakeholders' responses

The ability to produce energy while also offsetting carbon emissions is a strong driver for the adoption of BECCS mentioned in the literature on this LMT. However, socio-cultural barriers are not well explained in the literature, with further research pending. However, both the available literature and the stakeholders mention a lack of technical knowledge, storage and transportation and lack of

supporting policies and societal support. The high technical complexity of the process is a primary concern amongst the stakeholders, which is further hindered by the long-term uncertainty amongst the stakeholders about profitability and reliance on the technology, owing to a critical lack of good research on the topic. However, forest owners are becoming increasingly interested in BECCS due to its immediate financial co-benefits.

3.8.1 Stakeholders' perception of risks

Competing policies

- Industrialized countries buy certificates from other countries, rather than reducing their own emissions. [CH9]

Technical

- Increased upscaling means higher complexity, leading to increased difficulty to implement. [SE3]
- Slow interactions with the land means long term lock-in of its usage, with a long return time on investment. [SE5]
- High competition for biomass/low availability of biomass, leading to limited upscaling potential. [CH9] [SE5]
- Focus on highly technical solutions, such as biomass growth for BECCS, might lead to adverse consequences.
 - o Establishment of new monoculture. [CH9]
- Lack of knowledge among key stakeholders. [SE5]
- Risk of leakage in transport and storage stages of supply chain. [SE9]

Social

- The land-use sector, in general, is a highly contested space, difficult for political and public discussions. [SE9]

Financial

- The financial case for this technique is still unclear. [SE5]
- Large financial investments are needed to set up complex value chains. [SE5]

Security

- Uncertainty for technique implementation and permanence, for instance from climate change, is not discussed extensively among stakeholders. [SE5]
- Focus on BECCS might cause technological lock-in, while better options appear in the future. [SE5]
- Long timelines of land-based mitigation implementation have inherently higher risk due to uncertainty. [SE9]
 - o Especially in emerging economies, for instance due to risks of land conflicts. [SE9]

- A reduction in livestock numbers could decrease the availability of manure [NL]
- Manure is retrieved mostly from intensive farming. A future switch to more extensive farming because of animal rights could affect the availability of manure [NL]

3.8.2 *Stakeholders' perceived co-benefits*

Technical

- Biochar is both a source of feedstock and can be added to land to sequester carbon, fulfilling a dual role. [SE9]
- Sweden has some of the best conditions for BECCS in the world to capitalize on. [SE5]
- Increased demand for forest products synergizes with increased forest carbon sequestration. [SE8]
 - o Land-owners will be incentivized for improved forest management. [SE8]

Social

- Forest owners are increasingly interested in BECCS. [SE10]

3.8.3 *Stakeholders' perceived trade-offs*

- There is a choice between prioritizing negative emissions and fuel production. [SE3]

3.8.4 *Gaps observed based on stakeholder insights*

- Regulations need to be locally adapted to respond to the national/local context. [SE5]

3.9 Wetlands

Wetlands are estimated to make up around 5-6% of the Earth's land surface (Mitsch and Gosselink, 2015) and are one of the most productive ecosystem environments. Its landscape function contributes to the cycle of carbon water and nutrient, supports biodiversity, stores a rich variation of genetic materials, and provides food and materials for animals and humans (e.g., rice production) (Matthews, 2013). Wetlands are broadly defined by the Ramsar Convention or the convention on Wetlands (1971) as "areas of marsh, fen, peatlands or water, whether natural or artificial, permanent or temporary, with water that is static or flowing, fresh, brackish or salt, including areas of marine water...". There are widely accepted wetland types broadly classified under 3 categories (Matthews, 2013):

1. Marine & Coastal Wetlands
 - Marine: coastal lagoons, rocky shores, and coral reefs
 - Estuarine: deltas, tidal marshes, and mangrove swamps
2. Inland Wetlands
 - Lacustrine: connected with lakes
 - Riverine: connected with rivers and streams
 - Palustrine: forested/non-forested peatlands marshes, swamps and bogs
3. Human-made wetlands
 - Fish/farm ponds, irrigated agricultural land/paludiculture, salt pans, reservoirs, gravel pits, sewage farms and canals

In LANDMARC, our case studies cover mainly inland wetlands (riverine and palustrine), human-made wetlands (agricultural land), and estuarine (mangroves).

Canada: palustrine/peatlands (industry)

- Protection, reclaiming (needs defining), restoration (back to original state), conversion (converting to another landscape- e.g. grasslands, forest lands),

Sweden: forested peatlands (agriculture)

- Rewetting, revegetation

Netherlands: drained peatlands for irrigated agricultural land/paludiculture

- Rewetting, paludiculture, converting to another landscape- e.g. grasslands, forest lands),

Indonesia: Mangrove and peatland management (in industry and agriculture)

- Within the last decades, 6 out of 14.4 million ha of peatland has been converted from natural peat forests into agricultural land and industrial plantations. To address this problem, The Inonesian ministry MOEF established the Peatland Restoration Agency (BRG) in 2016 to manage and facilitate **peatland restoration in seven priority provinces**, which makes up around 40% of the nation's total land area: **Riau, Jambi, South Sumatra, West Kalimantan, Central Kalimantan, South Kalimantan, and Papua**. Peatland restoration targets: BRG

targeted to restore a total of 3.35 million ha of **degraded peatland** by the end of 2020, consisting of 2.5 million ha from rewetting, 670,000 ha from revegetation, and the last 185,000 ha revitalisation programme. By the end of 2020, BRG had managed to restore 25% of its target (835,288 ha). With the four-year extension from 2020-2024, BRGM has additional time to hit the target. **Revegetation** is a form of carbon sequestration process starting with natural carbon capture by plants followed by carbon storage when peat mass is formed. Hence, revegetation contributed to climate change mitigation through enhancing carbon stock. The target of revegetation by 2020 covers 670,000 ha of peatland.

Revitalisation: By 2020, 185,000 ha of peatland is targeted to be restored for economic purposes (revitalisation activities) through **paludiculture and agrisilvopasture** (a combined land management system between **agricultural components or activities with forestry and livestock/animal husbandry** to overcome land availability problems and increase land productivity, especially on marginal land).

Overview of stakeholders' perception of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs

Interviewees note that there is a great need for correct implementation of wetland rewetting, restoration, and management techniques. Specifically, including indigenous and local knowledge and respecting requirements should be a priority as there is a pre-existent insufficiency in social awareness and political motivations. This lack may hinder implementation or lead to adverse long-term results. Moreover, competing policies, conflicting interests, and a lack of proper administration amongst the different levels of the government are risks for implementation. These in turn influence a potential return on investment, which creates financial uncertainties.

There are issues regarding landownership that need to be carefully considered and resolved before adoption of different techniques. Stakeholders note that a decentralized policy measure would aid in implementation as current research on policy implications is scattered and inadequate, however this would be very context specific. The critical lack of knowledge indicated by stakeholders and lack of propagation of the advantages of this technique is also an issue.

However, the growing perception of climatic problems combined with the availability of indigenous knowledge that can be used is a significant driver for this technique. An important and sensitive issue to consider before adoption is also the historic trauma of the indigenous communities related to land-use and ownership.

Comparison of literature review and stakeholders' responses

The available literature on restoration of wetlands indicates that this LMT is crucial for carbon sequestration and increase in land productivity as wetlands cover about 5-6% of the Earth's surface. Stakeholders' perceptions differ in the need for correct implementation of technique as well as the application of available indigenous knowledge in tandem with pre-existing technology. Competing policies and lack of proper administration were also noted by the interviewees. An important barrier

highlighted by both sources was the issue of land-use and ownership for restoration concerning indigenous communities and marginal land.

3.9.1 *Stakeholders' perception of risks*

Competing policies

- Competing interests between government levels.
 - o Local governments do not see return on investment from national government mandates. [ID2]
- Institutional misalignment. [ID2] [ID7]
 - o Different development plans at different levels of government. [ID2]
- Complex governance. [CA3]
 - o Different approaches between national and provincial/local government. [CA3] [ID7]

Political

- Lack of political support. [ID2]
- Adverse political incentives. [CA6]
 - o Land concessions near elections. [ID2]
- Lack of continuity between administrations. [ID2] [ID7] [CA3]
- Corruption. [ID2] [ID7]
- Lack of proper indigenous community consultation. [CA5] [CA7]
- Land ownership.
 - o Indigenous land ownership should not be impacted by mitigation needs. [CA5]
- Long lead-in time to policy changes. [DE2]

Technical

- Use wrong technique implementation for restoration. [CA2] [CA3][CA5] [CA6] [CA7]
 - o Uplands, rather than wetlands. [CA3]
 - o Not fully restoring land to previous use. [CA7]
 - o Not done with indigenous knowledge/indigenous use in mind. [CA5] [CA6] [CA7]
- 'Double' accounting of carbon offsets, as ecosystems are already providing services. [CA2] [CA3]
- o Lack of good MRV framework. [CA7]
- Lack of good research on policy implications. [CA7] [CA3]
- Infrastructure challenges. [ID2]
- Technical capacity. [ID2] [ID7]
- Unclear definitions among researchers, practitioners. [CA3]
- Long term sustainability unknown. [CA6]

Social

- Community opposition to technique. [ID7]

- Lack of information, dissemination on technique benefits. [ID7]
- Land users reluctance to change current techniques. [ID7]
- Lack of youth involvement. [CA4]
- Lack of access for outsiders. [CA6]
 - Indigenous worldview does not align with outsiders' view. [CA6]

Financial

- Strong land-use competition.
 - Market demands for conventional agriculture use of land. [ID2]
- Trade imbalances, lack of return on investment. [ID2] [DE2]
- Oligopoly/market domination providing adverse incentives. [ID2] [ID7]
- Access to capital. [ID7]
- Long/no return on investment (without continuing carbon credits). [CA3]

3.9.2 *Stakeholders' perceived co-benefits*

Policies

- Decentralization of implementation program would aid in local implementation. [ID7]
- Indigenous rights, advocacy, could strengthen technique implementation. [CA5]

Technical

- Strong knowledge base in indigenous communities. [CA2]

Social

- Growing perception of climate change effects. [CA2]
- New approaches to land-use are starting to happen, including co-creation with communities. [CA4]

3.9.3 *Stakeholders' perceived trade-offs*

- Conventional use has high economic benefits.
 - Use for oil. [CA3] [CA5]

3.9.4 *Gaps observed based on stakeholder insights*

Stakeholders

- Need to shift away from a resources focused economy. [CA4]
- A lot of knowledge gaps on the system – how will technique implementation (or lack of) affect the region, other parts of the world. [CA3]
- Trauma (of the land) is an important aspect for indigenous communities that does not receive attention. [CA6] [CA7]

3.10 Pasture management

Pasture management is defined as a set of practices that ensure year-round availability of grazing pastures while also maintaining soil quality and biodiversity. The pastures that occupy low-fertility soils are the main source of animal feed and the introduction of small measures such as adding manganese to the soil and balancing grasses and legumes, biomass production can be tripled in grasslands with rapid increase in soil organic matter too. This also leads to a reduction in nitrogen fertilization which promotes floristic biodiversity.

Summary of LMT literature review LANDMARC D6.1

Pasture ecosystems cover approximately 25% of the Earth's terrestrial area, with Eurasia alone supporting 9.3 million km² of pasture (Liu *et al.*, 2019). The shift from natural to biodiversity seeded pastures can result in an estimated carbon sequestration potential of 6.48 tCO₂/ha/year over a period of 10 years (Teixeira *et al.*, 2011). Studies show that converting agricultural land to pastures can create carbon sinks which increase the SOC by about 5% annually (Conant, Paustian and Elliott, 2001; Conant *et al.*, 2017). Globally, soil carbon sequestration in grassland systems has a global mitigation potential 37–800 Mt CO₂/yr according to studies building on empirical data (Godde *et al.*, 2020).

A lack of soil correction and limited use of precision agriculture reduces the biomass potential and therefore mitigation of CO₂. Farmers need technological support and mentoring to optimize mitigation, but such mentoring is expensive. Pastures without animals can also lead to an increased risk of fires. Therefore, there is a need for a minimum stewardship to reduce such risks while maintaining the economic viability of the activity.

Overview of stakeholders' perception of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs

Interviews discussed a lack of policy incentives and an incongruence between regional and national politics regarding the implementation of pasture management, which are significant political barriers to implementation. Furthermore, increased bureaucracy and unsuitable policies resulting from lack of knowledge amongst policymakers is an issue. Interviewees noted a lack of available and future workforce resulting from the reluctance of the next generation to work in the countryside. This is a prominent social barrier to the adoption of this technique. Furthermore, there are several financial uncertainties and risks involving high investment costs for the technology and a reliance on uncertain government subsidies. However, the financial co-benefits, such as the promising nature of the carbon market, quick pay-back period and employment opportunities created by the implementation of the LMT are noteworthy drivers for implementation.

Comparison of literature review and stakeholders' responses

A large portion of GHG emissions is a consequence of animal-based food and food products according to the literature, which makes pasture management an important LMT to consider. Farmers need technological support and guidance for implementation, but such mentoring is expensive and inaccessible, as cited in the literature as well as by the involved stakeholders.

Additionally, the literature discusses safety concerns due to the lack of animals on pastureland, while the stakeholders mainly argue that there is a critical lack of workforce and trained personnel as people do not want to work in rural areas anymore. There are difficulties faced by the farmers in acquiring land and high technology costs, as highlighted in the interviews. Furthermore, lengthy bureaucratic procedures to implementation and lack of supportive policies are also unattractive prospects as seen by the stakeholders.

3.10.1 Stakeholders' perception of risks

Competing policies

- Lack of continuity between administrations. [ES6]
- Differences in regional policies. [ES10]
- Mismatch between Continental and national politics. [PT8] [ES10]

Policies

- Lack of knowledge and efficiency to manage incoming investments.
 - o EU rural development money not used well for agroforestry. [ES10]
- Lengthy bureaucracy for managing agroforestry on pastures. [ES10] [ES6] [ES9]
- Policies do not support sustainable pasture management. [ES5] [ES6] [ES7] [ES9] [ES10]
 - o This is due to a lack of knowledge and awareness among policymakers. [ES6] [ES7]
 - o New techniques promoted by climate action plan are not necessarily more sustainable. [ES7]
- Pasture management is administratively complex, situated between agriculture and shrubland. [ES8] [ES10]
 - o Large areas needed. [ES8]
 - o Lack of knowledge on benefits of sustainable pasture management. [ES6]

Technical

- Dependent on machinery and seed suppliers. [PT8]
- Lack of knowledge on new technologies for implementation. [ES7]
- Lack of awareness of subsidies. [ES9]
- Climate change affects technique implementation.
 - o Extreme conditions affecting old and new plantations, causing uncertainty. [ES9]

Social

- Farmers do not feel supported in sustainable pasture management by policymakers. [ES8]
- Lack of generational change/knowledge transfer.
 - o New generations do not want to work in the countryside. [ES6] [ES7] [ES8] [ES9] [ES10]
 - o Lack of knowledge transfer. [ES6] [ES9] [ES10]

- Partially due to small profit margins. [ES8]
- High land costs make sustainable pasture management inaccessible to young people. [ES10]
- Lack of societal environmental awareness driving unsustainable behaviour. [ES9]
- Reluctance to change existing pasture management approaches. [ES10]
- Lack of workforce. ES9] [ES10] [PT8]

Financial

- Long investment time. [ES10]
 - Coupled to uncertainty for receiving subsidies due to bureaucracy. [ES10]
 - Acquiring land to increase range has long payback time for pasture management (when compared to eg photovoltaic power). [ES5] [ES8] [ES9]
- Technique increases costs for pasture management. [ES5] [PT8]
 - Lack of knowledge among landowners necessitate specialised labor. [ES6]
 - High technology costs. [ES6] [ES10]
- Predominantly smaller lands/smallholders with small profit margins means innovation is difficult. [ES8]
- Greater remuneration required. [ES5]
 - Climate Action Plan contribution to sustainable pasture management remuneration negligible. [ES6]
- Reliance on subsidies for implementation. [ES10]

Security

- Uncertainty about return on investments. [ES6]
- International wars and changes in international economy. [PT8]

3.10.2 Stakeholders' perceived co-benefits

Policies

- New climate action plan provides opportunities for pasture management. [ES5] [ES7]

Technical

- New technologies available at low cost to aid implementation. [ES9] [ES10]
- Farmers are well informed and have good capacity. [PT8]

Social

- Sustainable pasture management directly contributes to social opportunities.
 - Profitability, economic value, employment, population drift. [ES5]

Financial

- Improved pasture investments pay back quickly. [ES5]

- Low risk on investments. [ES7]
- Carbon markets can be an opportunity, if priced right. [ES7]

3.10.3 Stakeholders' perceived trade-offs

Stakeholders did not note any trade-offs.

3.10.4 Gaps observed based on stakeholder insights

Stakeholders

- No (financial) tool to support mitigation in sustainable pasture management

3.11 Integrated fire management practices

Indigenous fire management refers to the use of specific indigenous knowledge to avoid forest fires and to make use of land for subsistence. Fire management is a key tool for the survival of many indigenous people around the world (Arroyo-Kalin, 2012; Mistry *et al.*, 2019). This practice also has social, cultural, and economic reasons linked to the livelihood of these indigenous people.

Historically, indigenous people managed fire by cultivating forests with plant species that are specifically tolerant to fire. Today, most indigenous fire management methods are combined with modern burning methods to prevent large fires (Levis *et al.*, 2018).

Summary of LMT literature review LANDMARC D6.1

Fires produce a significant number of GHGs that contribute to global climate change (Randerson *et al.*, 2012). The global mitigation potential of fire management ranges from 0.16 to 0.41 Gt CO₂e/year (Griscom *et al.*, 2017). Several fire management projects deployed in Brazil and yielded significant emissions reductions relative to the baseline. However, fire suppression policies and activities demand financial, human, and technical resources beyond national capabilities and budgets (Bilbao *et al.*, 2021). There are strong cultural prejudices against the use of fire management in protected areas, particularly in Latin America. The application of fire management may also disrupt the culture of indigenous or aboriginal people. Remote detection and monitoring technologies are critical for the implementation of fire management. These systems should also inherently have fire-fighting bodies to prevent risks. More studies need to be done on the behavior of fire and its effects under field conditions, the associated costs and impact on biodiversity. Exchange of knowledge and skills between different sectors of the society must be encouraged to identify and optimize best practices (Bilbao *et al.*, 2021).

Overview of stakeholders' perception of risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs

Interviewees especially note the difference in political motivations at national and regional levels and a lack of resources for implementation. There is a lack of resources to monitor and manage the technique, resulting from a lack of trained personnel. Furthermore, factors such as corruption and ambiguity surrounding political decisions contribute to the delayed adoption of the technique. Positive drivers for implementation are mainly social with a general willingness to apply the technique with proven examples, along with security co-benefits in terms of improvement of infrastructure protection.

Comparison of literature review and stakeholders' responses

Indigenous knowledge about fire management practices is an important aspect for the successful implementation of this technique, as found in the literature and in stakeholder interviews. The literature also mentions strong prevalent cultural prejudices against fire management and concerns over the disruption of the livelihood of indigenous communities. Exact knowledge about associated costs and impact on biodiversity is also unclear in the literature. Stakeholders mention a lack of favorable policies and political ambiguity on the national level regarding this practice. There is also a

lack of resources and trained personnel according to the stakeholders. However, the positive impacts on infrastructure are well understood by the stakeholders, as also indicated in the available literature.

3.11.1 Stakeholders' perception of risks

Competing policies

- There is a mismatch between national, regional, and local scale politics at times. [VE2]
- Lack of alignment between institutions on national forest management policy implementation. [VE2]
- Economic activities are allowed in protected areas, competing for land-use/development. [VE2]

Policies

- Corruption. [VE2]
- Ambiguity of political decisions for implementation of technique. [VE2]
- Due to decentralization, it is unclear who manages the forest, and who bears responsibility. [BF1]

Technical

- Lack of resources for monitoring, maintenance of technique. [VE2]
- Access to knowledge/implementation to upscale technique is difficult.
 - o Trained personnel are mainly located in centralized areas, rather than rural/remote areas. [VE2]
 - o Limited logistics possible. [VE2]

Financial

- Lack of resources for implementation of technique. [VE2]

3.11.2 Stakeholders' perceived co-benefits

Policies

- Favourable laws and policies at national scale.

Social

- Fire management is a traditional forest management technique, with existing community practice. [BF1]
- Communities are willing to apply new techniques, have successful examples to learn from. [VE2]

Security

- Positive impacts to infrastructure.
 - o National electric system as wildfires endanger logistics, hydroelectric power stations.
[VE2]

3.11.3 Stakeholders' perceived trade-offs

- Communities fear negative effects on employment due to environmental protection policies.
[VE2]

3.11.4 Gaps observed based on stakeholder insights

Stakeholders did not note gaps in the interviews.

4. Modelling stakeholders' perception of risks, co-benefits and trade-offs

In this section, modellers representing land use models, (DayCent, ALCEs and LandSHIFT) and a macro-econometric model (E3ME) broadly reflect on how their models can potentially consider the risks identified by stakeholders in section 3. A short summary of each model is also provided as a reference point (see D5.1 Development of National Model System for further details).

4.1 DayCent

Daycent is a *landuse biogeochemical ecosystem model* that can be applied for individual LMTs. DayCent can potential link information gather from in-situ Earth Observation tools to model the potential of a single LMT from the parcel level to the national level. DayCent will be applied to 10 number of case studies).

General description: DayCent is a daily-time step biogeochemical model of intermediate complexity that simulates ecosystem processes associated with carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) cycling, such as changes in soil organic matter, plant growth, nutrient availability and trace gas emissions in response to changes in climate, soil and land management.

In general, the capabilities of risk, co-benefits, and trade-off assessment with DayCent are limited to biogeochemical processes, such as reversibility of carbon sequestered in soil or biomass, climatic risks due to drought, changes in distribution of rainfall, and trade-off risks (e.g., yield). Risks and co-benefits that are not part of these processes, e.g., linked to availability of external inputs to soils, such as manure, need to be considered in scenario building or in setting the right boundary conditions. The same is true for co-benefits, e.g., it should be possible to reach a land equivalent ratio > 1 in agroforestry systems. The model also explores one LMT at one time thus does not explore trade-offs between different LMT applications.

We have used DayCent in the Swiss case study to illustrate the trade-off between higher soil carbon stocks and lower yields (about 30%) in organic agriculture. For reduced tillage, it seems that while the potential soil carbon sequestration is maximally half that of organic agriculture, there is not necessarily a trade-off with yield, which is expected to remain the same in reduced or no-till systems. This might provide some insights to stakeholder's concerns for impacts on yields and perceived trade-offs considering different techniques.

In the case of Kenya and ISFM, the first results of our national DayCent model application tells a somewhat different story. Our first results indicate that there is a co-benefit between higher soil carbon stocks with ISFM and higher yield.

Overall, most of the risks that stakeholders have mentioned seem to be of political, technical, financial, and social nature. As stated before, these may be important for setting the right boundary conditions for DayCent (e.g., in ISFM, we have, in accordance with stakeholder discussions, opted for a maximum yearly application of farmyard manure equivalent to 2t C per ha and year, only half of

the high rates from the long-term experiment used in CS9). A direct consideration of such forces in biogeochemical models, such as DayCent, is possible in coupled modelling frameworks that include agents-based models (e.g. (Marohn *et al.*, 2022)). However, such a hard-coupling of different models is highly challenging and beyond the scope of LANDMARC.

4.2 ALCES

ALCES flow was specifically developed for LANDMARC case study leads with no prior modelling knowledge, and/or use in co-creation workshops with stakeholders. It is applied in 10 number of case study countries.

General description: ALCES flow is a land-use exploration model that uses stakeholder inputs to explore scenarios for the short to mid-term. It models land-use related LMTs with a novel approach for including stakeholder information and knowledge. The tool has been developed to provide a low barrier approach to co-creation of scenarios and land-use simulations with stakeholders. The model has the capacity to explore a portfolio of LMTs and thus is able to assess trade-offs between different LMT options.

Stakeholder inputs in ALCES flow are captured in a direct and indirect manner. First, their information can be used as inputs to directly inform the following:

- Carbon: More detailed information that stakeholders might have on the carbon effects that LMTs portfolios have on land-use.
 - And subsequently provides information on the extent of stakeholder knowledge.
- Location: Where LMTs within an LMT portfolio are applied.
 - And why the LMTs should be applied there.
- LMT applied: To what extent the LMT portfolio is applied.
 - And why to this extent.

Indirectly, stakeholder information can provide context for designing the scenarios. These can be co-created on the spot with the stakeholders during a workshop and can also be based on the information that was captured in the surveys for this report. As such, the risks and co-benefits resulting from the interviews predominately provide the context for scenario explorations with the ALCES model. The risks and co-benefits related to implementation are interpreted as optimistic and pessimistic implementation of LMT portfolios, which can then be presented to stakeholders for further exploration.

As ALCES models for the short to mid-term (up to 2030), existing implementation risks and co-benefits can be directly interpreted as impacting optimistic and pessimistic implementation of that LMT. For example, risks that are unlikely to be mediated in the short term will likely have a strong impact on the implementation of that LMT in the short term. For instance, the lack of political, financial, or knowledge capacity to implement an LMT such as in agroforestry and wetlands is an example that would have an immediate impact on its upscaling in the short term. For LMTs with a short turnover time, such as organic agriculture, this could be a less 'serious' risk when compared to LMTs with a long turnover time, for instance agroforestry.

The risks that were mentioned by stakeholders which are related to lock-in of the land can be modeled in the choices that stakeholders make. This is reflected in ALCES through designing the LMT portfolio, and determining to what extent and where the portfolio is applied.

Another example are the risks and co-benefits related to infrastructure, and (lack of) access to resources in remote areas. These can direct where to apply the LMT portfolio, as well as provide understanding of why stakeholders apply the LMT to that extent in the area. A lack of infrastructure could lead to certain regions being 'left behind' for

Finally, trade-offs concerning land-use, for instance between carbon maximization and food production, are modeled by the ALCES model.

The ALCES model is a tool for land-use simulation and scenario exploration, strongly focused on co-creation with stakeholders. While some of the socio-economic, political, and technical risks are not directly modeled, they can be integrated through providing a contextual basis for scenario development. They also provide a knowledge basis for discussion and interactions with the stakeholders – exploring risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs with the stakeholders through a visual way in workshops.

4.3 LandSHIFT

LandSHIFT-N (national) is a *land system model* and its model result can be used as inputs to LandSHIFT-G (global) and EC-Earth Global atmosphere & carbon cycle model in WP7. LandSHIFT-N will be applied to 3 case studies at the national level.

General description: LandSHIFT is a spatially explicit model that simulates land use change dynamics and competition between different land-use activities (e.g., settlement, crop cultivation, livestock grazing, forestry) on grid level. Cell size varies between 250m for regional level applications and 5 arc-min in the global model version. Temporal resolution is between 1 and 5 years. The model downscales land-use drivers on the regional/country/local scale (e.g., demand for agricultural and forest products or LMT targets) to the grid cell level.

The LandSHIFT-N model simulates future land use and land cover of three case study countries resulting from changing demand for land of three competing categories of land use activities (crop production, livestock farming, and settlement). It uses a medium reference scenario (2020-2050) which prescribes area demand for settlement and agricultural production for food supply. As input information for the (additional) realization of LMT options, the model requires the quantity of area on which a portfolio of LMTs will be realized, in addition to a start date and a rate of realization. Information on the location or the most suitable areas for this activity is also required.

For example, the LandSHIFT-N model can take into account suitable areas for LMT implementation, such as degraded areas. These were mentioned in the context of stakeholder activities and can be implemented if spatial data is available. In addition, in cases where several LMTs compete for land (e.g. agroforestry and afforestation) a ranking/ prioritisation of LMTs is necessary.

In order to simulate LMT scenarios, the kind of information provided by stakeholder consultation cannot be implemented directly into the model since it focuses more on social, policy and financial aspects. However, the provided stakeholder insights are a valuable source to develop and enrich a limited number of scenario storylines. The co-benefits and risks, that are relevant for a country could, for instance, be translated into a scenario-specific set of measures and actions affecting the implementation and up-scaling of LMTs in a country. These actions together could, for example, either delay and/or hinder or promote the implementation of a particular LMT. This scenario-specific set of actions would need to be defined for each LMT option (e.g., agroforestry, paludiculture, etc.) and each scenario period (2020-2030 and 2030-2050). This information forms the backbone of the qualitative part of the scenario storylines, or scenario narratives.

To obtain the input for the LandSHIFT model, an additional step is necessary: qualitative pathways of LMT implementation have to be derived from the set of actions and measures, clearly distinguishing between the scenarios. For this purpose verbal expressions, such as “medium”, “slow” or “fast” could be used to describe the trend and pace of LMT development in a certain period of time. These terms can potentially be included in upcoming stakeholder workshops.

Subsequently, these qualitative trends have to be quantified in a meaningful, realistic and transparent way, e.g. by analysing historic trends or existing policy targets.

This approach has several challenges. First, clustering the information in a limited number of scenarios that are plausible, consistent and most of all useful for stakeholders: This requires a well moderated process. And it requires time. Second, an important consideration is to determine at which step should stakeholders be involved, and where cooperation between modellers and CS leads is more efficient.

4.4 E3ME

E3ME is a *global macroeconomic model* with national level components that can be used to assess the potential policy portfolios to support the scaling up of LMT portfolios. Results can also help to inform the scaling up of continental policy portfolios for the most promising LMTs in different continents. The model is applied 7 case study countries.

General description: E3ME is a global, macro-econometric model designed to address major economic and economy-environment policy challenges. The mode includes integrated treatment of the world's economies, energy systems, emissions and material demands. This enables it to capture two-way linkages and feedbacks between these components. It can fully assess both short and long-term impacts. The time resolution is annual but if larger intervals are required, E3ME can interpolate. The time horizon of the LMT implementation and the policy is an important part of scenario design. Stakeholder engagement can contribute to guiding future trajectories (e.g., political and technological feasibility). E3ME currently solves to 2050.

E3ME is a macro-econometric model that integrates the world's economic and energy systems and the environment. It is primarily used for scenario analysis (i.e., difference from an established baseline) and can capture both overall macroeconomic impacts on jobs and economy, but also sectoral impacts. The model can consider LMT portfolios and their potential corresponding policies.

For the most part, there is no endogenous model treatment in E3ME of the technical details of different LMTs, nor of the impacts of LMT policies on LMT activities. When modelling LMT scenarios in E3ME, the scale of the LMT activity itself and the associated techno-economic factors (e.g. CAPEX and OPEX costs, CO2 emissions, etc.) are usually entered into the model by assumption. Thus stakeholder knowledge could potentially be in terms of their assumed outcome.

It is therefore important that these assumptions about potential LMTs incorporate a reasonable external assessment of costs, risks and co-benefits internal to the activity itself. This assessment could potentially be a useful contribution from the stakeholder engagement tasks to our modelling. For example:

- In the Canada case study, we modelled a scenario featuring restoration of peatland which had been degraded through oil extraction activity. A detailed set of input assumptions were required regarding the extent of peatland restoration, land management costs, potential carbon removals, and the quantity of oil production affected. It is important that these assumptions regarding the scale and costs of the LMT activity are realistic.
- In the Germany case study, we assumed an increase in forestry production. The E3ME modelling does not assess the feasibility of the scale of this increase, so the assumptions need to incorporate reasonable assessments of risks and opportunities.
- In the Netherlands case study, we assumed the development of new biogas with CCS plants. We effectively assumed that there are sufficient people with the necessary skills in place to build and run these plants, although this is a potential risk in scaling up this technology. We

also assumed that captured carbon was sold to other sectors, an opportunity that would otherwise have been missed in the endogenous model dynamics.

- In the Sweden case study, for lack of good data on which to base an assumption, we have not assumed any cost reduction from economies of scale in the rollout of biochar. This diffusion effect is a potential opportunity that is not captured in our modelling.

Once these technoeconomic assumptions are made, the added value of the E3ME model is then to estimate the impacts of the LMT activities on the macroeconomic and energy systems. E3ME is well-suited to capturing risks, trade-offs and co-benefits, to the extent that they exist within these macroeconomic and energy systems. For example:

- In Canada case study mentioned above, there is a clear trade-off between the health of the peatland, and the economic potential of the oil sector. Once the work of developing technoeconomic assumptions is in place, the E3ME modelling was able to assess the ultimate macroeconomic trade-offs between the lost oil activity, the additional employment from peatland management, and the revenues from carbon credits.
- In the Sweden case study, we modelled the impacts of carbon credits paid by the government for carbon removals from biochar and BECCS. However, in a scenario with a balanced budget, paying for these credits required raising tax rates for tax payers. This therefore creates a trade-off between the revenues received by the carbon-removing industry, and the cost to Swedish citizens from a higher tax burden.
- In the Germany case study, the increase in forestry output leads to co-benefits for the supply chain of the forestry sector, including for example the machinery required for management of forests.
- In the Netherlands case study, attention was paid to how peatland drainage can lead to soil subsidence and structural damage to property. Restoration of peatlands would therefore have the co-benefit of allowing costs from this damage to be avoided. However, even in the base case where the property is damaged, there is a compensatory benefit from the additional investment and employment required to maintain and repair the buildings. So the costs of the damage to the buildings (i.e. the stock of the nation's fixed assets) can be effectively traded off against the lost employment in the construction industry (i.e. the flow of national income).

In addition to the technoeconomic assumptions, there are potential *second-order* risks, opportunities, co-benefits and trade-offs of LMT activities that are not covered by the E3ME model. Again, these can be modelled by assumption, although in many cases the expected impacts are negligible (especially when modelling at a national level), so consideration needs to be given as to whether the time invested in developing assumptions is worthwhile. These second-order dynamics include (but are not limited to):

- Impacts of climate change (which may be marginally impacted by negative emissions from LMT activities) on economic output and productivity.

- Impacts of the LMT activity on biodiversity, and corresponding feedbacks to economic output and productivity.
- Health co-benefits from cleaner air.

5. Further exploration of risks, co-benefits, trade-offs

5.1 Reflection on further exploration

Considering the outcomes of the stakeholder interviews, we reflect on some areas that can be further explored to gain a better understanding of the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs of land-based climate mitigation portfolio. This can include:

1. **Risks:** What is the best way to capture the risks identified by stakeholders in the short, mid- and long-term?
2. **Co-benefits:** Identifying and quantifying the co-benefits of land-based climate mitigation, such as increased biodiversity, improved soil health, increased water quality, improved human health, and enhanced ecosystem services. How do these co-benefits contribute to sustainable development goals? Furthermore, how do some of the environmental co-benefits align with the perceived needs, risks, co-benefits and trade-offs as defined by the different stakeholder?
3. **Trade-offs:** Understanding the potential trade-offs between different land-based climate mitigation options, such as afforestation vs. reforestation, bioenergy vs. carbon sequestration, and land-use change vs. agricultural productivity, and how these trade-offs can impact different stakeholders. These were underreported by stakeholders but play a prominent role in mitigation LMT literature. For example, food security concerns for agroforestry or reforestation. Models that can consider LMT portfolios such as ALCES, LandSHIFT, and E3M3 can potentially evaluate these trade-offs, which can help stakeholders at different scales with decision making. DayCent can provide insights for land use managers, while ALCES outputs may be interesting for communities, regional decision makers. LandSHIFT results could be useful for setting sectorial agendas at the national level.

Trade-offs between mitigation and adaptation needs is a prominent consideration when understanding a portfolio. One example would be from forest management – an adaptation measure might need to reduce tree stand to establish species better adapted to changing climatic conditions, but this could reduce carbon stocks.
4. **Governance and policy:** Analyzing the governance and policy frameworks needed to support effective implementation of land-based climate mitigation strategies, including issues related to land tenure, land-use planning, monitoring, and reporting, and financing mechanisms. How can we align the different perspectives on risks, co-benefits and trade-offs while maximizing carbon sequestration at different governance levels?
5. **Social and cultural dimensions:** Exploring the social and cultural dimensions of land-based climate mitigation, including issues related to Indigenous rights, community engagement, and local knowledge, and how these dimensions can impact the effectiveness and sustainability of mitigation efforts. We noted that different sets of stakeholders have very different interpretations of issues such as land-use, restoration or rehabilitation of land, and the possible effects and intended effects of LMTs. For example, they might prioritize cultural use over carbon sequestration as a priority, with carbon sequestration being a side-effect over restoring the land to its original state.
6. **Technological innovation:** Examining the role of technological innovation in supporting land-based climate mitigation efforts, such as the development of new monitoring tools, carbon accounting methods, and land-use planning software.

7. Dynamics over time: LMT implementation as well as associated risks, co-benefits and trade-offs emerge at different points in time. There might be late co-benefits from establishing new forests, for example the supply of timber. An assessment of co-benefits and trade-offs thus needs to consider such time dynamics. Similar dynamics are associated with climate change feedbacks and the need for adaptation measures, e.g. establishing more diverse forest stands might imply slower growth and thus reduced sequestration rates. However, in the long run higher resilience of diverse forest stands leads to reduced disturbances and potential releases of carbon from these.

By exploring these areas, it is possible to gain a better understanding of the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs of land-based climate mitigation portfolio and to identify strategies that can maximize mitigation benefits while minimizing negative impacts.

5.2 Reflection on links to LANDMARC climatic risk assessment and risk management plan

The implementation of LMTs implies changes in land use, which implies further consequences than, for example, the implementation of a technology. Such transformations can conflict with a society's fundamental values, such as the way they are managing businesses that had been their source of income for generations, or changing the landscape as they have known for decades to introduce techniques they are unfamiliar with. Mitigating climate change is often not on top of their priorities. Besides, many compensation mechanisms are still not well established and are subject to regular changes depending on politics, feeding this feeling of uncertainty. It is not a surprise that, despite scientific evidence suggests that most LMTs can yield good results in terms of mitigation, the general position of most land users is of reluctance.

However, according to the responses of the interviewees analyzed in LANDMARC's deliverable 4.1, the adaptation benefits linked to LMTs often outweigh their mitigation potential. This means that it is the land user who is benefiting directly from implementing these techniques by solving issues that are high priorities in their daily agendas. From D4.1, it could be extracted that most LMTs can play a major factor in reducing erosion and improving the quality of the soil. These are major concerns for many land users, who see these elements as becoming further deteriorated because of the effects from climate change. Ecosystem services associated with LMTs, such as an increase in biodiversity and pollination are often difficult to monetize but contribute to higher yields and a decrease in pests. Despite the LANDMARC project being focused on climate change mitigation, it must be acknowledged that adaptation and long-term sustainability are the main strengths of most LMTs, tackling problems that are direct concerns for most land users.

The growing disconnection between the environmental sciences community and land users, who often perceive the latter as a threat to their interests, could challenge the implementation of sustainable techniques, resulting in worse consequences for land users in the long term. It is

therefore crucial to find common ground and emphasize these effects when presenting LMTs to stakeholders, so they can identify how these techniques benefit their interests.

Many LMTs do not start yielding adaptation benefits until years, sometimes decades, after their implementation, but require upfront investments. From the policy point of view, their mitigation potential could be used to help covering the costs of these initial phases through revenues obtained in the negative emissions market, serving as an incentive for land users to adopt these techniques.

6. LMTs to LMT portfolio

6.1 Moving from singular LMTs to an LMT portfolio

One of the features of LANDMARC is moving beyond singular LMTs, and analyzing different portfolios of LMTs. However, there are currently no approaches for starting an analysis like this. There we propose a practical approach for moving from a singular LMT (DayCent) analysis to an LMT portfolio (ALCES, LandSHIFT, E3ME):

1. Develop a baseline for the LMT: Start by developing a baseline scenario that reflects current land use practices and emissions levels. This can be based on existing data, stakeholder knowledge, and modeling tools.
2. Identify mitigation options for an LMT portfolio: This could include options such as reforestation, afforestation, conservation agriculture, agroforestry, peatland restoration improved grazing management, and others. Consult individual LMT experts and carry out literature review to identify LMT potential. Estimating the emissions reduction potential can be based on existing data sources, ground truthing (in-situ measurements, EO tools) and modeling tools (such as Daycent and ALCES), as well as expert knowledge and experience.
3. Estimate costs and co-benefits: Estimate the costs and co-benefits associated with each mitigation option. This could include factors such as the cost of implementation, the potential for co-benefits such as biodiversity conservation or improved soil health, and any trade-offs or risks associated with each option. LMT experts and literature can be consulted to verify estimates.
4. Develop a portfolio of options: Use the emissions reductions potential, costs, and co-benefits estimates to develop a portfolio of options that collectively offer the best balance of mitigation benefits and risks (using tools such as ALCES, LandSHIFT, E3ME). If possible, verify LMT portfolio with experts/stakeholders.
5. Model the portfolio: Model the emissions reductions potential and costs of the portfolio of options using existing data and modeling tools. This will help to estimate the overall impact of the portfolio on emissions reductions and the associated costs.
6. Monitor and adjust the portfolio: Monitor the effectiveness of the portfolio over time and adjust it as needed based on changing conditions or new information based on stakeholder consultations.
7. Present results (including important assumptions or provides access to these assumptions) including trade-offs or synergies between different LMT portfolio options

Overall, modeling a portfolio of land-based mitigation techniques and practices requires a detailed understanding of the emissions reduction potential, costs, and co-benefits associated with each option, as well as the ability to integrate these estimates into a comprehensive modeling framework.

Estimates and assumptions should be made transparent (documenting the methodology and the primary and secondary data collected with stakeholder engagement and existing sources). Stakeholders' assumptions should not be taken as a given if it cannot be triangulated with other sources; but their assumptions can be used as a potential scenario option. By developing a transparent and evidence-based model of the portfolio of options, decision-makers can more effectively prioritize and allocate resources to the most effective and sustainable land-based mitigation strategies.

Notably, this does not account for the qualitative risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs that we have identified in this report. This is often seen as a difficult step to include for most models. As the modelling teams note in their reflection on the stakeholder interviews, most of the data is useful to inform the scenarios used in the model, or provides a contextual basis that informs the scenarios, and subsequent workshops with the stakeholders. The E3ME model can to a limited degree include some aspects noted by stakeholders through assumptions. But in general, directly modelling many of the factors is difficult to account for in current modelling approaches. This is especially so when considering a LMT portfolio rather than a singular LMT.

Stakeholders were understandably reluctant to provide information beyond their expertise, and generalists were difficult to identify and interview for our case study teams.

On the other hand, stakeholders were receptive to an initial round of co-creation workshops and scenario exploration, making use of LANDMARC model outputs to inform the workshop and understand stakeholder perspectives.

The LANDMARC consortium has identified suitable portfolios for each case study country, and now has reports on the climatic effects of LMTs (D4.1), and socio-economic, political, and technological effects (D5.2) for LMTs at the national scale. These can form the contextual basis for a more informed series of stakeholder workshops to move from analyzing a singular LMT to a portfolio as a whole. Using scenario exploration tools such as ALCES, and modelling the effects through DAYCENT, LandSHIFT, and E3ME, the LANDMARC consortium can present a holistic overview of an LMT portfolio to stakeholders.

6.2 Risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs in LANDMARC LMT portfolios

The LANDMARC case studies have each determined the LMT portfolio based on an iterative process including literature review and (multiple) stakeholder sessions. shows the latest insights from the updated narratives in LANDMARC D2.6, showing the latest updates to the LMT portfolios.

Table 6. LANDMARC LMT portfolios per case study. The green color indicates the main LMT focus (or case study partner specialization). The green color indicates the other LMTs of the portfolio.

LMT	DE	NL	PT	ES	SWE	CH	UA	BF	KE	NP	VN	CA	VE
Agroforestry		Green	Blue	Blue		Blue	Blue	Green	Blue	Blue	Green		Green
Rice management										Green			
Reduced tillage						Blue	Blue						
Integrated soil fertility management								Green	Green				
Organic agriculture			Blue			Blue	Green			Blue			
Biochar					Blue	Blue					Blue		
Afforestation/ reforestation		Blue		Blue				Blue	Blue			Green	
Forest management	Green		Blue	Green	Blue			Blue		Blue	Blue		
Forest fire management													Green
Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS)		Blue			Blue		Blue						
Anaerobic fermentation of manures (biogas/compost)													
Peatland management		Green										Green	
Pasture management			Green	Green									

We then categorised the stakeholder insights from section 3 into country LMT portfolio. This information has been presented to further inform the scenario building for modelers, as well as to provide inputs for further stakeholder outreach, through workshops or dissemination. The insights from these tables, coupled to the modelers’ reflections and data presented in section 3 can be a starting point for the discussion of model outputs, providing a qualitative framing that would otherwise be missing. Note that we do not present this a representative distribution of the importance of certain risk, co-benefit, and trade-off categories.

Germany LMT portfolio

Germany LMT portfolio	Competing Policies	Policies	Technical	Financial	Social	Security	Co-Benefits	Tradeoffs
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Forest Management	8	14	8	10	7	2	6	0
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Netherlands LMT portfolio

Netherlands LMT portfolio	Competing Policies	Policies	Technical	Financial	Social	Security	Co-Benefits	Tradeoffs
Agroforestry	11	15	16	33	15	2	28	2
Afforestation/Reforestation	2	17	19	9	8	6	22	3
BECCS	2	0	13	4	2	7	7	2
Wetland Management	10	19	27	23	10	0	10	3

Portugal LMT portfolio

Portugal LMT portfolio	Competing Policies	Policies	Technical	Financial	Social	Security	Co-Benefits	Tradeoffs
Agroforestry	11	15	16	33	15	2	28	2
Organic Agriculture	19	33	37	16	29	5	32	2
Forest Management	8	14	8	10	7	2	6	0
Pasture Management	7	20	8	16	21	4	16	2

Spain LMT portfolio

Spain LMT portfolio	Competing Policies	Policies	Technical	Financial	Social	Security	Co-Benefits	Tradeoffs
Agroforestry	11	15	16	33	15	2	28	2
Organic Agriculture	19	33	37	16	29	5	32	2
Forest Management	8	14	8	10	7	2	6	0
Pasture Management	7	20	8	16	21	4	16	2

Sweden LMT portfolio

Sweden LMT portfolio	Competing Policies	Policies	Technical	Financial	Social	Security	Co-Benefits	Tradeoffs
Biochar	0	9	27	19	7	0	9	2
Forest Management	8	14	8	10	7	2	6	0
BECCS	2	0	13	4	2	7	7	2

Switzerland LMT portfolio

Switzerland LMT portfolio	Competing Policies	Policies	Technical	Financial	Social	Security	Co-Benefits	Tradeoffs
Agroforestry	11	15	16	33	15	2	28	2
Cropland management	19	33	37	16	29	5	32	2
ISFM	7	7	11	5	10	2	4	0
Biochar	0	9	27	19	7	0	9	2

Ukraine LMT portfolio

Ukraine LMT portfolio	Competing Policies	Policies	Technical	Financial	Social	Security	Co-Benefits	Tradeoffs
Agroforestry	11	15	16	33	15	2	28	2
Cropland management	19	33	37	16	29	5	32	2
Biochar	0	9	27	19	7	0	9	2
BECCS	2	0	13	4	2	7	7	2

Burkina Faso LMT portfolio

Burkina Faso LMT portfolio	Competing Policies	Policies	Technical	Financial	Social	Security	Co-Benefits	Tradeoffs
Agroforestry	11	15	16	33	15	2	28	2
ISFM	7	7	11	5	10	2	4	0
Afforestation/Reforestation	2	17	19	9	8	6	22	3
Forest Management	8	14	8	10	7	2	6	0

Kenya LMT portfolio

Kenya LMT portfolio	Competing Policies	Policies	Technical	Financial	Social	Security	Co-Benefits	Tradeoffs
Agroforestry	11	15	16	33	15	2	28	2
ISFM	7	7	11	5	10	2	4	0
Afforestation/Reforestation	2	17	19	9	8	6	22	3

Nepal LMT portfolio

Nepal LMT portfolio	Competing Policies	Policies	Technical	Financial	Social	Security	Co-Benefits	Tradeoffs
Agroforestry	11	15	16	33	15	2	28	2
Rice management	4	3	5	3	4	0	2	0
Organic Agriculture	19	33	37	16	29	5	32	2
Forest Management	8	14	8	10	7	2	6	0

Vietnam LMT portfolio

Vietnam LMT portfolio	Competing Policies	Policies	Technical	Financial	Social	Security	Co-Benefits	Tradeoffs
Agroforestry	11	15	16	33	15	2	28	2
Biochar	0	9	27	19	7	0	9	2
Forest Management	8	14	8	10	7	2	6	0

Canada LMT portfolio

Canada LMT portfolio	Competing Policies	Policies	Technical	Financial	Social	Security	Co-Benefits	Tradeoffs
Afforestation/Reforestation	2	17	19	9	8	6	22	3
Wetland Management	10	19	27	23	10	0	10	3

Venezuela LMT portfolio

Venezuela LMT portfolio	Competing Policies	Policies	Technical	Financial	Social	Security	Co-Benefits	Tradeoffs
Agroforestry	11	15	16	33	15	2	28	2
Integrated Fire Management	6	5	5	2	0	0	6	0

Note that the climatic co-benefits are not listed in this deliverable but are covered by D4.1. Overall stakeholders were mainly comfortable discussing one LMT at a time. This clustering of LMT portfolios is the first qualitative representation of contextual risks (policies, technologies, finance, society, security) across different LMTs in our project. The LMT portfolio heat map can highlight areas of concern. For instance, policy and financial risks are consistently mentioned in many country case studies. Thus, further exploration of policy risks is required, for instance, in multi-level policy making or institutional support, and financing instruments that adequately address this risk, either by more nuanced policies or through better access to financing. Future studies are also needed to explore in greater detail if these risks are representative of individual LMT and if there are additional risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs in LMT portfolios within and across a region.

7. Conclusion

Methodology

The approach was changed from a standardized survey to a semi-structured interviews based on piloting phase with case study leads. The case study teams were provided with a generic list of interview questions that covered climatic risk (inputs for D.4.1 *Climate risk assessment and initial risk management plan*) and qualitative social economic risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs of LMTs (inputs for this deliverable). We initially set out for an MCDA methodology, but this required some consistency to be applied. We found that LMTs have a strong practice component that varied widely across contexts and thus MCDA methods were not sufficiently flexible for our research. Semi-structured interviews allowed us to have more in depth responses covering the complexity associated with individual LMTs, but at times also covering multiple LMTs. Thus, we decided to move forward with an analysis that allowed stakeholders more freedom to illustrate their perspectives.

Key findings

Interviews were coded in accordance with the categorization of important themes, and subsequently clustered per LMT. The outcomes were compared the literature review from D6.1 *Literature review of LMT potential*. Our overall findings were that the literature review focused more on technical potential and climatic risks. Stakeholders tended to focus on their individual circumstances, including finances, livelihoods, and the lack of (access to) technical knowledge. Other commonly discussed issues mentioned by stakeholders were land tenure and a lack of continuity for the next generation, mainly for LMTs on private or leased land. Governance was also an issue consistently brought up across all LMTs, including institutional (mis)alignment, consistent policy messaging and policy support, and long-term policy continuity (with changes in government). Long term LMT strategies are particularly important for LMTs which require a longer CO₂ sequestration period (i.e., forests and peatlands). Across all LMTs, the return-on-investment period was raised as an opportunity and as a concern. Opportunities arise from new CO₂ revenue generation stream as well as more sustainable land management. However, there were concerned regarding changes to current livelihoods or current and/or traditional practices, particularly regarding the costs of applying LMTs that impact yields or outputs.

We synthesised stakeholders' perspectives in heatmaps that highlighted the frequencies of risks and co-benefits. There were very few trade-offs mentioned. This is where models (DayCent, ALCES, LandSHIFT and E3ME) could potentially be introduced to co-benefits and/or trade-offs within and between different LMTs and LMT portfolios.

We asked modellers to reflect on stakeholder preferences and indicate to which extent the risks, co-benefits and trade-offs can be included in models. Three of these models, ALCES, LandSHIFT, and E3ME, have the capacity to assess LMT portfolios.

Modellers viewed the qualitative risks identified by stakeholders to be useful in setting boundary conditions and developing scenario storylines. Including qualitative risks (including political, social, some technical and institutional risks) directly in these models may not yet be possible, but can be used as input for co-creation sessions with stakeholders. Financial risks are not covered in the land-based models but are covered in E3ME which considers social, economy-wide and economic risks.

Next steps

These findings are useful for researchers, policy analysts and modellers as they provide an initial succinct exploration of SH's perspectives on risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs. With this information

we will work on creating qualitative scenario that capture the complexity of individual and LMT portfolios, and where, possible quantity these risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs in scenarios. These qualitative and quantitative scenarios can be communicated back to the stakeholders and used for future LMT portfolio strategy development and inform potential policy mix development.

We also propose to LANDMARC case study teams to use this deliverable as a contextual basis for considering which SDGs most relate to their specific circumstance and stakeholder engagement work. This will link the more local case study context to the wider global community goals.

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9. Appendix

9.1 Interview Guidelines

Note: this interview guideline was part of a wider risk survey carried out in collaboration with D4.1 Climatic Risk Assessment. We only include the part of the interview survey related to D5.2 for risk and opportunities in scaling up of a LMT.

Interview guidelines for risks & opportunities in upscaling of LMT

Interview guideline step overview:

1. Send the GDPR consent form. **The consent form must be sent out no less than 48 hours before the interview.**
2. Send the **pre-selection form** at least **48 hours** before the interview. Fill in the already known information in section 1 with the goal of saving time.
3. **Show table 3** to the stakeholder and bring up the topics of discussion (in bold), with the help of examples of parameters within the topic (in bold, black letters). **Write the notes in each topic's tables (tables 4 to 12) and come back to table 3 after the topic has been discussed to continue to the discussion.**
4. Ask the stakeholder the **closing-up questions** at the end of the questionnaire.
5. **After the interview, write a 1-2 pages summary with the main outcomes of the interview.** The goal is to document all the ideas that couldn't be recorded by the survey.

Overview:

1. Read introduction
2. Show table 3 to the stakeholder and start a dialogue with the stakeholder about the topics (in bold), with help of the examples (in bold back) to help trigger ideas.
3. Write any relevant observations from the stakeholder in the tables referring to each topic (tables 4 to 12). If the discussed topic does not fit with any of the categories described on the tables, use the provided blank space.
4. When you've finished taking the notes, come back to table 3 to continue discussing the next topic, and continue this process until all relevant parameters have been addressed.

Estimated time needed: ~30mins.

Introduction guidelines for CS lead:

The following questions are meant as a (semi-structured) interview guideline. The outputs of these efforts will be used to inform a survey focused on a greater reach of stakeholders based on the breadth of information collected in the interviews. The following categories are meant as a starting point for the dialogues and customization of the (structured) interviews. CS/Regional lead can make changes as they see fit based on their literature review, expertise, and interactions with the consortium such as modelling teams.

In this part, we ask you to evaluate the risks in the implementation LMT could face from different stakeholder perspectives across 9 risk contextual categories (see Table 3).

To complete this part, it is important to define the concept of “risk”. **Risks** refer to a specific possible outcome that is perceived to be negative, varies across scales: time scale, governance scale (national provincial/local-national government), area of location and size of land are highly dependent on your perspective. Therefore, we aim to gather your perception of risks in LMT you have experience with.

By **risks**, we mean the **barriers** to implementing land-use based mitigation options or potential **negative outcomes** of implementing the land-use based mitigation option.

On the opposite side of risks we have **opportunities** that can **enable** the implementation or scaling up of an LMT and have **positive impacts**. Thus opportunities are also based on contextual factors as listed in Table 3 below) including technology, politics, policy, institutions, society, economy/market, businesses and the environment.

We refer to 9 main contextual categories of risk in Table 3:

Table 3: Contextual factors for impact: barriers and enablers to implementing LMT	
1.	Technology/practice parameters: Land-use based technology/practices risks refer to the negative impact the technology may have on people or the environment or challenges to implementing and/or scaling up the technology (e.g. technical challenges, scalability challenges, accidents, failure of the technique to reach its targets...)
2.	Political parameters refer to policy choices that cause dissent and disputes among political actors and groups within the same or different jurisdictions (e.g. lack of political support, political instability, corruption...)
3.	Institutional parameters refer to implementation challenges and opportunities, lack of coordination or conflict within or across institutions, or a lack of institutional legitimacy (e.g. institutional misalignment, long/tedious bureaucracy, exceptional institutional support, lack of institutional legitimacy, inclusion of LMT in national NDC...) <i>Note:</i> Institutions are defined as “formal and informal rules and norms that organise social, political and economic relations” ^[1] (North, 1990). They may include policy, education, market, religious, and cultural institutions
4.	Policy parameters refer to challenges and opportunities with implementing policies such as policy instruments, regulations, strategies, programmes and initiatives (e.g. poor policy design, challenges with policy implementation, strong policy support, lack of adequate monitoring...)
5.	Societal parameters refer to the social support towards implementing a technology such as threatening societal groups and/or creating inequalities among them (e.g. proximity of the technology to communities, social changes, local culture, lack of knowledge, resistance to behavioural change, preference for the new scape, negative health impacts, impact in daily life of locals...)
6.	Economy-wide factors refer to the influence of policies on national economic indicators, which might affect specific stakeholders such as public or private organizations, local SHs (e.g. trade imbalances, energy security, market regulation, lack of subsidies, market domination...)
7.	Business factors refer to specific challenges and opportunities related to running a business including investment challenges, payback periods and revenue stream (e.g. investment challenges, more diversified sources of income, high capital costs, long payback period...)
8.	Environmental factors refer to changes in the nature/environment including human, flora and fauna ecosystems (e.g. biodiversity loss, waste issues, increase in biodiversity...)

9. **Avoided costs** derived from the implementation of LMT (e.g. **avoided infrastructure expenses due to avoided soil subsidence, avoided costs in water purification because of avoided chemical substances leaching...**)

Table 3

Thus both risks and opportunities could take place at different temporal and spatial scales. Increased risk could be an immediate effect of a technology or practice being implemented, or it could only be relevant decades from now. The risks could also be different at different spatial scales: for example, at a local scale, there could be more immediate environmental effects that might not be relevant at a national scale. Finally, the time dimension of risks could be different at different scales: countrywide risks might not be apparent for decades, while local risks are felt more immediately.

The temporal scale is interpretable as seasonal/cyclical/recurring and singular events. In some cases, stakeholders will understand events to be part of a cycle: for example, a political season of 1-4 years, re-occurring environmental events, or implementation delays. In other cases, stakeholders will put forth singular events: while risks due to worsening climate change could be cyclical (drought every 1-4 years, heatwaves in summer, hail in winter), the risk of an overall loss of land due to a climate shift and its change in land use (and associated cultural/institutional/economic consequences) might be a singular event risk – in the near or distant future. In these guidelines, we aim to capture both interpretations that stakeholders might have for these risks – both the cyclical, and likely more near term, worries, and the singular events.

Please rate the risk & opportunity relevance following parameters for their importance to LMT, NA if the risk does not apply. Some specific fields are included and explained for each of the categories – the applicable time scale and spatial scales. For all fields, we have included space for explaining the answer and added a comment section for any additional remarks.

In the tables below we will refrain from using the terms risks and opportunities to avoid confusion. Instead, we will talk about risks as barriers and/or negative outcomes and opportunities as enablers and positive outcomes. We will simply refer to them as negative or positive impacts. Stakeholders intuitively can talk about negative and positive aspects without having to refer to our risk and opportunity framing.

4.1. Land-use based mitigation technology/practices risks (barriers/negative outcomes) & opportunities (enablers/ positive outcomes)

- Applicable time scale: for which time scale is this impact most relevant (months, years, decades...)
- Applicable spatial scale:
 - Technology implementation scale (individual, household, community, municipality, sub-national, national, supranational, global)
 - Technology spatial impact scale: at which technology scale does this risk take place? (Individual, household, community, municipality, sub-national, national, supranational, global)

LMT/Technological negative or positive impacts	Applicable time scale	Applicable spatial scale	Comments

Technical challenges: (high cost, unavailability of materials...)			
Infrastructure integration challenges			
Technological lock-in			
Scalability challenges			
Technical accidents			
Failure of LMT to reach mitigation targets and/or future reversal			
Failure of technology to reach adaptation targets			
Other technology impacts (free text)			

Table 4

4.2. Political risks (barriers/negative outcomes) & opportunities (enablers/ positive outcomes)

- Applicable time scale: for which time scale is this impact most relevant (months, years, decades...)
- Governance scale: at which governance scale does this impact take place? (community, city, province/state/national/Supernational/Continental/global)

Political negative or positive impacts	Applicable time scale	Applicable governance scale	Comments
Lack of political support (existence of higher priorities...)			
Political instability			
Corruption			

Other political risks (free text)			

Table 5

4.3. Institutional risks (barriers/negative outcomes) & opportunities (enablers/ positive outcomes)

- Applicable time scale: for which time scale is this impact most relevant (months, years, decades...)
- Governance scale: at which governance scale does this impact take place? (community, city, province/state/national/Supernational/Continental/global)

Institutional negative or positive impacts	Applicable time scale	Applicable governance scale	Comments
Institutional misalignment			
Exceptionally strong institutional support			
Lack of institutional legitimacy			
Inclusion of LMT within national NDC			
Other institutional impacts (free text)			

Table 6

4.4. Policy risks (barriers/negative outcomes) & opportunities (enablers/ positive outcomes)

- Applicable time scale: for which time scale is this impact most relevant (months, years, decades...)
- Governance scale: at which governance scale does this impact take place? (community, city, province/state/national/Supernational/Continental/global)

Policy negative or positive impacts	Applicable time scale	Applicable governance scale	Comments
Poor policy design			
Challenges with policy implementation			
Strong policy support			
Lack or inadequate monitoring and evaluation			
Long/tedious bureaucracy			
Other policy impacts (free text)			

Table 7

4.5. Societal risks (barriers/negative outcomes) & opportunities (enablers/ positive outcomes)

- Applicable time scale: for which time scale is this impact most relevant (months, years, decades...)
- Societal scale: at which governance scale does this impact take place? (individual, household, community, municipality, sub-national, national, supranational, global)

Societal negative or positive impacts	Applicable time scale	Applicable societal scale	Comments
Proximity of the technology to local communities			
Social changes			
Social injustice			
Resistance to behavioural change			
Societal resistance			
Preference for the new scape			
Local culture (social class, social rules...)			

Capacity gap (lack of knowledge...)			
Impact daily lives and practices of local communities			
Negative health impacts			
Other societal impacts (free text)			

Table 8

4.6. Economy-wide (barriers/negative outcomes) & opportunities (enablers/ positive outcomes)

- Applicable time scale: for which time scale is this impact most relevant (months, years, decades...)
- Spatial impact scale: at which technology scale does this impact take place? (Individual, household, community, municipality, sub-national, national, supranational, global)

Economy-wide risks negative or positive impacts		Applicable time scale	Applicable spatial scale	Comments
Trade imbalances				
Energy security challenges				
Market domination				
Market regulations				
Lack of subsidies				
Other economic factors (free text)				

Table 9

4.7 Business risks (barriers/negative outcomes) & opportunities (enablers/ positive outcomes)

- Applicable time scale: for which time scale is this impact most relevant (months, years, decades...)

- Spatial impact scale: at which technology scale does this impact take place? (Individual, household, community, municipality, sub-national, national, supranational, global)

Business negative or positive impacts	Applicable time scale	Applicable spatial scale	Comments
Investment challenges			
High(er) capital costs			
Long payback period			
More diversified sources of income			
Uncertain/revenue stream			
Other business factors (free text)			

Table 10

4.8. Environmental risks (barriers/negative outcomes) & opportunities (enablers/ positive outcomes)

- Applicable time scale: for which time scale is this risk most relevant (months, years, decades...)
- Environmental scale: at which environmental scale does this impact take place? (individual, household, community, municipality, sub-national, national, supranational, global)

Environmental negative or positive impacts	Applicable time scale	Applicable environmental scale	Comments
Land-use change			
Low emissions reductions potential			
Biodiversity loss			
Increase in biodiversity			
Water and soil management			
Other environmental factors (free text)			

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Table 11

Possibilities for avoided costs

Applicable time scale: for which time scale is this risk most relevant (months, years, decades...)

- Spatial impact scale: at which technology scale does this impact take place? (Individual, household, community, municipality, sub-national, national, supranational, global)

Possibilities for avoided cost	Applicable time scale	Applicable spatial scale	Comments
Avoided soil subsidence			
Avoided chemical substances leaching			
Other environmental factors (free text)			

Table 12

5. Closing-up questions

- Which is the main constraint to the implementation of the LMT in your opinion?
- Which of the opportunities are the most promising in your opinion?
- Would you invest in LMT if you had the resources? (yes/no)
- Why (not)?
- (To be filled by CS lead): Perceived singularities/vulnerabilities of the stakeholder)
- Are you interested in participating in future workshops and questionnaires?

^[1] North, D. (1990). Institutions, institutional change, and economic performance. New York: Cambridge University Press See in GSDRC: <https://gsdrc.org/topic-guides/inclusive-institutions/concepts-and-debates/defining-institutions/>